

Community Consultation Report

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC
Community Hub

GSC Auldhouse Foundation

GSC Auldhouse Foundation

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Data Availability: All materials used in this consultation are included in the report Appendices. This includes the Participant Information Sheets, Privacy Notice, Consent Form, Demographics Form, Discussion Questions (i.e. interview script), and code for the quantitative analysis. Raw demographics data and interview transcripts cannot be shared publicly and were permanently deleted upon completion of analysis to comply with GDPR. Photocopies of filled-in Consent Forms and necessary administrative documents (e.g. Data Management Plan, Retention Record, and etc.) have been retained for archiving purposes.

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1. About Us

1.1. The Team

Authorship:

Sara Eftekhari: Principal Investigator and Community Engagement Research Intern.

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Elizabeth “Liz” Millard: Research Assistant Volunteer.

- Roles (CRediT Taxonomy): Conceptualisation, Data curation, Investigation, and Writing – original draft.

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- Note: For comments, questions, feedback, or collaboration/funding opportunities, please contact Michelle Evans.

1.2. GSC Auldhouse Foundation's Community Hub

Established in 2024, GSC Auldhouse Foundation is a registered charity, formed by grassroots football club Giffnock Soccer Centre (GSC) when they relocated from Pollokshaws (Norwood Playing Fields) to Auldhouse (previously occupied by Hutchesons' Grammar School).

Communities in this area (e.g. Kennishead, Arden, Carnwadric, Eastwood, and etc.) have been directly affected by poverty, disadvantage, and lack of opportunity. As such, GSC Auldhouse Foundation is establishing a much-needed community hub for the people of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area.

The Foundation is about more than football. It aims to support the local community by giving them a place they can call their own and providing activities and programmes which are relevant to them; from football classes to yoga and everything in between.

We want this hub to reflect the voices of Ward 2 residents: what they need, what they care about, and what would help them and their loved ones. To do this, we carried out a community consultation in July 2025. We invited both residents and the people who look after them (e.g. the police, council workers, and other services), to share their experiences of life in the community and to suggest ideas for improvements.

The findings from this community consultation are presented in this report. It highlights the issues, needs, and priorities of Ward 2 residents and will provide evidence to help the Foundation secure funding for long-term, sustainable programmes and activities as voiced by the community.

This community consultation was funded by the University of Glasgow's Find A Solution 2025 programme, which provides resources to initiatives to meet local needs and make a positive difference.

1.3. Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn)

Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) is an electoral ward of Glasgow spanning Arden, Kennishead, Carnwadric, Mansewood, Hillpark, Newlands, Muirend, Pollokshaws, and Eastwood. Below, Figure 1 shows a map of the area:

Figure 1

Map of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn)

Note. Map from the City Population website (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the boundaries of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) outlined in green.

The 2022 Population Census counted a population of 24,392 for the area. According to the age distributions shown (see Figure 2), the population is stable and not growing in size, with early signs of an ageing population.

Figure 2

Age Distribution of the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) Population Split by Gender

Note. Population pyramid adapted from the City Population website (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the age and gender distribution of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) residents, per the 2022 Population Census.

Figure 3 shows that most Ward 2 residents (83.6%) reported they were born in Scotland or the rest of UK, while 16.4% were born elsewhere (Europe or Other country). This highlights a significant immigrant population.

Figure 3

Country of Birth of the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) Population

Note. Bar chart adapted from the City Population website data tables (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the country of birth of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) residents, per the 2022 Population Census.

Ethnically, Figure 4 shows 78.7% self-reported as White, with the following largest ethnic groups being Asian at 13.9% and African/Caribbean at 3.3%. This highlights the significant ethnic diversity of the area.

Figure 4

Ethnic Background of the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) Population

Note. Bar chart adapted from the City Population website data tables (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the ethnic background of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) residents, per the 2022 Population Census.

Figure 5 shows that most residents (89.4%) list English as their main language, while 10.3% list an "Other" main language that is not Scots, British Sign Language or Gaelic.

Figure 5

Main Language of the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) Population Aged Three or Above

Note. Bar chart adapted from the City Population website data tables (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the main language of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) residents aged three or above, per the 2022 Population Census.

Figure 6 shows that 42.7% of residents reported no religion, while 57.3% said they follow a religion. Most of those with a religion identified as Christian (42.1%) or Muslim (12%).

Figure 6

Religious Affiliation of the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) Population

Note. Bar chart adapted from the City Population website data tables (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the religious affiliation of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) residents per the 2022 Population Census.

2. Methods

2.1. Participant Recruitment

Only people aged 18 years or older who lived in, or had a strong connection to, Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) were interviewed.

Participants were opportunity sampled and recruited through word of mouth, via existing contacts of our General Manager Michelle Evans, and referrals from other participants. As a result, many of those interviewed were people working in roles that supported the community, since they were the easiest to reach, schedule, and most immediately willing to take part.

The participants included: parents whose children took part in GSC Auldhouse activities, people from local charities, staff from Glasgow City Council, public services such as the police and mental health services, community councils, nurseries, and other organisations.

Data collection was held throughout all of July 2025. As such, sampling was limited by people being away on annual leave or having slower response times due to the summer holidays.

2.2. Interview Procedure

Participants were interviewed either individually or in small groups, in-person (at GSC Auldhouse or another place chosen by the participants) or online via Microsoft Teams. Group interviews, which were limited to a maximum of five people to ensure everyone had enough time to speak, were held because they encouraged discussion.

However, opportunity sampling sometimes made it difficult to gather enough people for a group, so individual interviews were also held. These one-on-one sessions allowed participants to share their experiences and suggestions in depth, and also made it possible for those with limited availabilities to take part.

First, the participants were given a Participant Information Sheet with a Privacy Notice (see Appendix C), and a Consent Form (see Appendix D) and Demographics Form (see Appendix

E) to fill. The Participant Information Sheet had two versions which were worded slightly differently depending on the recipient: 'People' (see Appendix A) or 'People Who Look After the People' (see Appendix B).

The following demographic information was collected about them:

- Their age group
- How they were connected to the local area
- How long they had lived in Ward 2 (if they were currently living there)
- Their gender identity
- Their ethnic background
- Their full name and signature

Then they were guided through a semi-structured interview (see Appendix F for script) and asked about:

- What life is like in the community
- What challenges they or others face
- What the community needs most
- Their ideas for what could help the community and why
- What would make the new hub feel useful, welcoming and inclusive
- Suggestions for activities, spaces, or support services in the hub
 - ("spaces" meant what the building or outdoor areas could have: like a prayer room, a quiet space, a breastfeeding space, and etc.)

A semi-structured approach, where the script acted more as a prompt and flexible guide, was used to allow the discussion to flow more naturally and to encourage participants to share ideas and experiences more freely than they might in a rigidly structured interview.

Including the time it took to read the information and fill the forms, the interviews took approximately between 30 minutes to an hour and half. The sessions were audio-recorded using multiple recording devices for backup, auto-transcribed verbatim using Microsoft Word or Teams, and then analysed.

2.3. Participant Summary Statistics

A total of 29 people were interviewed. Of these, 22 identified as "Female", five as "Male", and two chose "Prefer not to say". This may reflect the tendency for many community-focused jobs (like those in charities, education, and health services) to have more female staff.

Additionally, 20 participants identified as "White or European", eight as "Asian or Asian British", and one as "Mixed or Multiple Ethnic Groups". This is similar to the ethnic distribution for Ward 2 shown in Figure 4.

The sample spanned a wide range of age groups. However, Figure 7 shows that most (12) participants were aged 35-44 years old. People under 18 years were not interviewed because it was difficult to get parental permission with opportunity sampling.

Figure 7

Age Group Distribution of the Community Consultation Sample

Note. Bar chart showing the age group distribution of the community consultation sample.

Altogether, the sample was skewed towards participants who were Female, "White or European", or aged 35-44 years old. This may partly reflect the general community demographics and the people who regularly engage with local activities, services and research. Their perspectives may be particularly useful because they may be the most likely to use the services the GSC Community Hub provides, meaning insights from these groups can help ensure what the hub offers meets their needs. Simultaneously, the underrepresentation of men, Black participants, and other age groups (particularly children) highlights missing viewpoints crucial to making the hub inclusive and attractive to all the community.

Figure 8 shows that the three most common connections to the area were "I currently live here" (19 participants), "I have family or close friends who live here" (15 participants), and "I work, study, or volunteer here" (15 participants). The nine participants who said, "I do NOT currently live here", all supported the community through their professional or voluntary roles, and thus had strong connections to the area.

Figure 8

Connection to Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn)

Note. Bar chart showing the types of connections participants reported having with the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area.

Among participants who currently lived in the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area, Figure 9 shows that most had lived there "10 years or more" (seven participants) or "5-10 years" (five participants). This indicates that most participants were very familiar with the area. But the perspectives of newer residents are important too, as they may have a fresher understanding of the challenges of integrating into the community.

Figure 9

Duration of Living in Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn)

Note. Bar chart showing, for participants who currently live in the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area, how long they have lived there.

Collectively, the participants showed long-term personal and professional connections to the area, indicating that their experiences and suggestions were relevant and dependable. However, the views mainly reflect the groups most represented in the sample; missing viewpoints must be noted and investigated.

2.4. Quantitative Analysis

Summary statistics and plots were wrangled, summarised, and visualised using the R programming environment (version 4.5.1, R Core Team, 2025), using the "tidyverse" package (version 2.0.0, Wickham et al., 2019).

Figures 2 to 6 were created from data on the City Population website (Brinkhoff, 2024), showing the population of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) from the 2022 Population Census. See Appendix G for the R markdown code.

Figures 7 to 9 were created from demographic data manually typed into a CSV file. See Appendix H for the R markdown code.

All plots were designed to be colour-blind friendly and remain distinguishable if printed in greyscale, ensuring visual accessibility of the report.

2.5. Qualitative Analysis

With each interview, new ideas emerged, which were carried forward and helped shape discussions in later interviews. Over time, similar experiences and suggestions appeared across multiple interviews, saturating into key ideas, or *themes*.

The original plan was to use Braun and Clarke's (2006) *thematic analysis*, which would have involved exhaustive, line-by-line coding of the transcripts to explore every possible theme and sub-theme. However, due to time and workload restrictions, *rapid qualitative analysis* (Vindrola-Padros & Johnson, 2020) was used instead.

Rapid qualitative analysis is faster and focuses on practical insights rather than exploring every possible idea in depth. The goal is to quickly identify patterns and useful ideas that can inform action. This makes it well suited for a community consultation project, where the priority is to understand participants' experiences and suggestions in a way that can guide decisions. The method emphasises capturing clear, broad, and actionable themes in participants' own words.

In this vein, themes were identified and organised in a rough mindmap from the researcher's recall, based on recent and close exposure to the interviews. The themes were split between problems and actionable solutions based on what the participants had shared, and colour coded in the mindmap as shown in Figure 10. Audio recordings were then revisited to select specific quotes to illustrate key points.

Figure 10

Screenshot of Zoomed-In Mindmap of Themes

Note. Screenshot of a zoomed-in section of the mindmap containing all the recalled themes. The themes have been colour-coded: blue backgrounds show solutions suggested by the participants, and red backgrounds show problems they identified.

2.6. Reflexivity

As a young (18-24 years) female researcher with a background in Psychology, from an "Asian or Asian British" immigrant background who presents as "White or European", my *positionality* influenced both access to participants and interactions during data collection.

Positionality refers to the ways my social identity, background, and personal characteristics shaped how I was perceived and interacted with participants. How approachable or agreeable I was perceived may have affected a participant's willingness to take part in discussions, particularly with opportunity sampling done using word-of-mouth, where first impressions and immediate rapport made a difference in who decided to participate. My background and values made me particularly attentive towards including perspectives from female, immigrant, asylum seeker, ethnic minority, LGBTQIA+, and neurodiverse participants. This reflects both my personal motivations and professional commitments to inclusivity and amplifying the voices of groups who face discrimination. It is a key reason why I was chosen as the researcher for this project.

Men were less represented, partly due to low numbers in the settings I opportunity sampled from, and partly because some of the men available may have felt more reluctant to participate due to my positionality. Black participants were also harder to recruit, again due to low numbers and perhaps my perceived ethnicity.

These factors shaped not only which perspectives were most accessible to sample, but also how I interpreted participants' experiences. My understanding was inevitably shaped by my own life experiences, social identity, and the *intersectionality*, i.e. overlapping, of factors in my background (e.g. my age, gender, ethnicity, and etc). This allowed me to better engage with and understand some aspects of participants' experiences, while leaving my perspective more limited in others. This is a natural part of qualitative research. Being aware of this helps explain why certain groups may be more represented in the sample due to my positionality or reasons beyond my control, and highlights the need to interpret the findings with this context in mind.

2.7. Ethical Considerations

GSC Auldhouse Foundation acted as the Data Controller for this project, not the University of Glasgow, so formal ethics approval was not required. Standard good practice was followed to ensure secure data management and fair treatment of participants, including completing a Data Management Plan (DMP), a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), a Legitimate Interests Assessment, and a Data Retention Schedule. Personally identifying

information was anonymised and redacted to minimise the risk of triangulation, where different pieces of information could be combined to identify participants. A qualitative research expert from the University of Glasgow reviewed the DMP and DPIA and provided feedback to further improve participant anonymity.

Access to raw data was restricted to trained researchers. Staff handling the raw data completed at least the University of Glasgow's free online training on Information Security Awareness and GDPR, while as project lead, I also completed Records Management training. Participants received a Participant Information Sheet with a Privacy Notice and a Consent Form, explaining the project, how their data would be used, and their rights. They were given time to read the information and ask questions before deciding whether to participate. Informed consent was obtained, and participants were reminded they could withdraw at any time. Children were not recruited as participants due to the challenges of ensuring their wellbeing, obtaining parental consent, and collecting meaningful data while using opportunity sampling.

Interviews were conducted in ever-changing locations due to opportunity sampling. Effort was made to create a quiet, private environment; however, this was sometimes challenging. Interviewers took care when listening and responding to sensitive information about local-area issues. For example, while immediate action on participants' suggestions was not possible by the hub, as securing funding, hiring new staff, and implementing suggestions required time and resources, participants were signposted to local charities and the community councils for support and follow-up where possible.

3. Results

3.1. Poverty & Basic Needs

3.1.1. Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation

The Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) ranks areas across Scotland from most to least deprived, using indicators such as income, employment, health, education, access to services, crime, and housing to paint an overall picture of socioeconomic disadvantage.

According to SIMD (2020) rankings, Carnwadric and Arden in Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) fall within the bottom 20–5% of most deprived areas in Scotland. Their immediate proximity to GSC Auldburn perfectly positions the community hub to directly serve residents facing the greatest socioeconomic barriers. As the closest neighbourhoods, they are likely to form a substantial portion of the hub's users and gain the most benefit from its programs. Other neighbourhoods, including Mansewood, Kennishead, Hillpark, and Pollokshaws also fall low in the SIMD rankings and could benefit from the hub too. In contrast, Muirend, Newlands, and Eastwood are among the most affluent neighbourhoods in Ward 2.

3.1.2. Affordability

As previously mentioned, GSC Auldburn Foundation was formed by Giffnock Soccer Centre (GSC) when they relocated from Pollokshaws to Auldburn. The football club, GSC, is the primary user of the Auldburn facility and the vast majority of club members are from East Renfrewshire, and therefore have more disposable income. GSC is run on a subscription model and as such high membership fees limit local residents' ability to partake in the club.

- By and large, football is the most popular participatory sport in the West of Scotland for children and young people. To provide affordable options for locals, GSC Auldburn Foundation has established Friday Night Football and Holiday Hope Camp 2025.
- Sustaining these programmes long-term requires consistent funding.
- A postcode-based discount on venue hire was suggested to make the premises more affordable and accessible for the local community. At present, the buildings are used mainly in the evenings, nights, and weekends by the club, leaving daytime hours underutilised. Likely daytime users are nearby residents, including primary

carers, older adults, and those limited by distance or mobility, who value the venue's convenient proximity. Discounts could increase use, attract volunteers, and boost community engagement.

- A key barrier is understaffing. At the time of writing, the Foundation currently has one employee (General Manager Michelle Evans) but requires the likes of a Programme Manager/Coordinator, Volunteer Coordinator, Youth Workers, Sports Coaches, and etc. to enable the smooth and consistent running of activities and programmes. Securing funding to bring these posts into being is urgently needed for the continued operations of the hub.

3.1.3. Food Insecurity

As a consequence of socioeconomic disadvantage, local residents face food insecurity.

Participants mentioned that Thornliebank Foodbank, located at the Thornliebank Resource Centre on Robslee Drive, has recently shut down.

- A "food pantry" or "foodbank" was commonly suggested by participants. Helping Hands Community Foodbank and the Auldhouse Community Foodbank offer valuable inspiration, and there is potential for collaboration to share knowledge, resources, and mutual support. Amongst supermarket options for acquiring food donations, Morrisons was noted for their Community Champions, who are staff members responsible for coordinating local donations and supporting community initiatives.
- Consider dignity and privacy; ensure collection methods minimise embarrassment and allow discreet access to items. One participant highlighted the importance of privacy and feeling safe: "I've got [several] children. Single mum. And there's been days, even recently, that I can't feed myself but I've got to feed the kids, but I'm too embarrassed to come down to the [foodbank] to let people know that I'm in need. Because I'm one of them people, like, I stand on my own feet and you'll never see me vulnerable. ... If somebody sees me vulnerable, because of how much I've picked myself up over the past [several] years ... it would knock me back down."
- Suggested discreet approaches include:
 - Home delivery or discreet drop-off locations

- Pick-up during low-traffic periods, or scheduled time slots to ensure privacy
- “Take what you need” trolley/box in a quiet area, allowing residents to take items without direct interaction
- The hub has worked with Foundation Scotland, Nourish the Nation (led by Sainsbury’s in partnership with Comic Relief), and Cash For Kids for food provision and funding for Holiday Hope Camp 2025.

3.1.4. Community Resource Sharing

Participants suggested running a range of community resource-sharing initiatives to reduce waste and allow access to items without cost. Ideas included:

- Inspired by the University of Glasgow's Eco-Hub, a similar model was suggested for the community hub. At the Eco-Hub, donated clothes are available for swapping, but can also be purchased at low cost (£1 or £2.50) to fund the Eco-Hub. Students donate kitchen and household items, which others can take for free (up to five items at a time). The idea being to encourage donation and reuse. Similarly, there could be a donation of unwanted clothes, household or kitchen items at the community hub so others in the community can swap for them or buy them for cheap.
- Toy swaps, where children’s toys can be exchanged (or bought for cheap) rather than discarded, creating a community toy bank.
- Eastwood Nursery School has a foodbank and a second-hand shop that sells items like clothes and shoes. Instead of duplicating efforts, the hub could work with the nursery, run joint donation drives, and direct people to their foodbank or shop.
- The hub currently has a bookshelf with sports books. This could be developed into a Little Free Library or as part of a Bookbug programme, where residents can take a book and leave one in return, allowing the collection to grow beyond sports.
- A tool library was suggested to share resources for hobbies, crafting and repairs, such as sewing machines. This could take the form of a Repair Café, which would allow intergenerational knowledge sharing and community support. Inspiration can be taken from Repair Café Glasgow.
- Collaboration with charities like Bike for Good, to provide free/cheap bike repairs, refurbish bikes, or offer training on bike maintenance on a weekly or monthly basis.

3.2. Cultural Integration & Inclusivity

3.2.1. Racism

Ward 2 has a significant immigrant population and is ethnically diverse (see Figures 3 to 5). This is important as immigrants may face barriers, or *friction*, in navigating society, such as language difficulties, challenges with paperwork, lack of familiarity with local services, discrimination, and subsequently social isolation. These obstacles make it harder to find jobs, access opportunities, or get help from services, and fully participate in community life. This can affect wellbeing, financial stability, and inclusion, and can lead to scapegoating and further racism in a harmful feedback loop. This highlights why it is important to anticipate, prevent, and address the challenges immigrants face, in order to ensure fair access to services, promote inclusion, and support the wellbeing of all residents.

Asian or Asian British participants described how their children were often racially stereotyped: "I would say definitely our children are being discriminated. ... there is definitely people who think differently about our children. And the Scottish people, they would say that these children are making more noise than the other ones. What to do?" The participant described others projecting negative traits, like disruptive behaviour, onto their children. This illustrates how racism can create a self-reinforcing cycle of discrimination. The children's mere existence and appearance triggered assumptions and skewed perceptions, which were then "confirmed" through these projections.

Another participant illustrated how projections and assumptions of negative attributes, and hostility, when unaddressed, can escalate into public verbal abuse, intimidation and fear for personal safety:

- One participant described being accused of making noise and yelled at with abusive language because of their visible Asian identity. "... we were walking around and some people like. They said that we are making noises but at the same time when other people were making noises as well. For example, we are Asians, they can see that from our attire that we are Asian. So there's there's just like made this thing an issue that why are you making noises and this is not nice. And they yelled actually. ... They didn't talk to us nicely. ... They just yelled, yeah. ... So and then and then some Scottish people, they. What the other guy- he was calling us? Pakistani? Paki?"

- "Yeah, some some abusive language [inaudible] Paki. ... He was actually, he was shouting and ... he was in the bus stop and we were walking."
- "... we actually got afraid. We thought that he might have something sharp with him. ... So we found it threatening actually to be honest. So we didn't like it. I'm telling you these issues since like last week. Like these things happen."

Another participant shared similar experiences of racism, recalling that people made insulting, inaccurate and bad faith assumptions about their literacy, qualifications, and reasons for moving to the area based on their appearance and clothing: "So we are being judged because of our attire, like my friend mentioned or clothing or the way we live. They believe that we are illiterate, but we are not. The other day when we were speaking to a lady in the city centre, she said that what made you come here? We said that we are qualified, right? Like [another participant's spouse] is an engineer and she said why you came here. And [another participant] mentioned that [their spouse] was already working in [country outside UK] and [major UK company] gave him a job. And so we are we have come here on proper visas. So don't judge us on the way we are. See we are not the ones."

They also described facing exclusionary attitudes: "When you read the comments of literally Scottish people, they say that we don't own this area, now the other people are invading our spaces." They revealed local resistance and the incitement of hostility along lines of ethnic differences.

A parent emphasised the role of colourism in discrimination towards their children:

"Whereas they are Scottish. They are classed as citizens. So why? It's just the colour of their skin? That's the only thing. Whereas if you're just going to speak to other kids, then the accent is same. They speak the same. You know, the way the other people, ... talk. But it's just the colour. Skin colour." This shows how even when children shared language, accent, upbringing environment, and social norms with peers, any visible difference made them targets for exclusion. This highlights that discrimination often may arise from superficial visible traits rather than the person's character or abilities. Thus showing the importance of the hub defining belonging by shared responsibility for and pride in an area, rather than visible markers of ethnicity, faith, or culture. Differences always exist; whether small or

large, visible or unseen. So communities embracing diversity fosters social integration, acceptance, and cohesion.

Participants expressed a desire for opportunities for exposure, mixing and familiarisation between ethnicities. One parent explained: "... I wish there would be more events where we get together, where children at least get together, get along with each other, so they could see that Asian children are also well mannered. We teach them manners. So it's not just the Scottish children who should be privileged to have everything. So there should be more events where our Asian children can also participate"

- "But the thing is, the initiative that Michelle has taken for the children to play together, there will be more tolerance and patience. That's one step that most children are playing together. They will be more patience and tolerance towards our children. So I would appreciate there would be more events where children ... [interacted]." Alongside existing activities mentioned by this participant (e.g. Friday Night Football), General Manager Michelle Evans is currently looking into accessing funding for an Integration Programme to address social integration issues and racism.
- Shared activities could help children be seen as individuals rather than an ethnic monolith, challenge stereotypes, and promote equitable participation. Participants of different ethnic backgrounds commonly suggested cultural exchange events of sharing food. They cited similar past events they had enjoyed and highlighted the benefits, expressing a desire for more of these events in their local community.

3.2.2. Engagement, Inclusion & Advocacy

3.2.2.1. Community Councils & Public Engagement

In Glasgow's Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn), several active community councils play a pivotal role in advocating for residents' rights and providing forums to raise concerns so residents can access support, and have a say in local governance. Key names include: Newlands & Auldburn Community Council; Pollokshaws & Eastwood Community Council; Mansewood and Hillpark Community Council; and DACK Community Council, which serves Darnley, Arden, Carnwadric and Kennishead.

Community councils are volunteer-run, with membership open to residents aged 16 or over who are registered to vote. Members are elected every four years, usually in October, and vacancies between elections are filled through co-option (appointment by existing council members) or by interim elections if enough places are vacant.

- GSC Auldhouse currently hosts the Pollokshaws & Eastwood Community Council meetings every other month, which are open for attendance to the public and other relevant stakeholders such as the police and Glasgow City Council officials.
- Community councils face challenges engaging the wider public, and public attendance at these meetings can be low.

3.2.2.2. Social Clusters & Barriers to Participation

Participants widely noted that residents often formed social clusters along ethnic, cultural, or religious lines, interacting primarily within their own groups rather than the wider community. Participation in activities were often shaped by both ethnicity and faith. For example: "White or European" residents may attend predominantly white or white Christian groups; "Black, Black British, Caribbean or African" residents may attend groups of their own ethnic background or Black church services; and "Asian or Asian British" residents may have their own networks or mosque communities. These clusters can create silos, where social support, information, and resources are largely confined within each group. As a result, some community activities or opportunities can feel inaccessible or less appealing to those outside these groups, reducing broader public engagement and attendance.

One resident explained:

- "... probably the reason behind it is because you say, well, what's the point of going? They're all white people, ... They're not going to listen. They're having their own gathering. And obviously, ... if you have like hospitality like for food or drinking or that, you'll have your own kind of food. Which, being Muslims or Indians, whatever, you can't eat that kind of food. Then say, what's the point of going there? So they they will back off that way as well. ... to have a proper gathering and like have mix,

what dietary, whatever religion have, then people you know, turn up. Say, so now that's alright. Just give it a go, you know? They're listening."

- "Not being cheeky or anything, but having a white person all the time, now what's the point of going? That white person is going be there, ... talking to their own. They have ... their own food, alcohol. Don't feel comfortable about religion. Beliefs and all that comes in. Do I go there? Never mind, never mind. Going there, never mind. You know? They'll come in, in that way. Go just back out, you know? Don't see what's the point."

The participant underscored barriers such as dietary and faith differences, feeling overlooked and dismissed, and the perception that events which were presented as open to all but saw low attendance from other groups, was because the event primarily catered to white participants, which did not automatically welcome, appeal to, or include other groups.

- One size does not fit all, and participation requires deliberate, targeted catering, ideally through a representative from the group who can engage that group directly.
- Figure 5 shows that 42.1% of participants identified with a Christian denomination and 12% as Muslim. This information highlights religious holidays and events that may generate demand for venues, activities, and attendance. It can guide targeted and inclusive programming (e.g. a quiet clean space to pray), or inform activities such as hosting Eid, Easter, or Christmas at the hub, with opportunities to collaborate with local churches and mosques. People may be drawn to the hub for these group-specific events but stay engaged through broader activities like Friday Night Football, enabling exposure, interaction and familiarisation between residents of different backgrounds.

3.2.2.3. Representation & Advocacy

These issues of engagement and inclusivity also extend to community councils. As membership is volunteer-based and vacancies can be through appointment by existing members, this can favour more privileged residents who have time, social connections, and familiarity with the existing community council. Councils that feel predominantly white, and

religiously or culturally homogenous may unintentionally exclude residents outside that group, reducing broader community engagement.

- **!** Efforts by community councils to recruit members from underrepresented backgrounds, whose lived experiences are valuable for advocating for the residents who are often overlooked or dismissed, have faced challenges and frustrations.

A resident shared:

- "No disrespect to them and I'm not being racist or anything, but see how you're always like in some communities, you you have like Asian women, Pakistani, Indian women wouldn't feel comfortable talking to a white woman. So having a representative for ... Asian culture, talking to them in their own language, you feel wait a minute, I can talk to that woman. I wouldn't feel comfortable talking to you, but I would talk to her."
- In order to find a representative, they said, "You got to attract them and listen to them. Listen to what they want. ... And say, we're willing to help you, but are you willing to come forward? Represent your own community? ... you need an Asian representative, right? Just to, to attract, you know, Asian men or women. Say like, we want you, which one of you is willing to get? And someone that comes all the time. We should be able to say, you know what? I'll take it. I'll represent the Asian community. And the, to feel comfortable to talk in their own language. Then they could talk to you in their own language. No disrespect, but not everyone knows English." Another participant chimed in, "Especially old people."
- The other participant continued to add, "I think it's just about the opportunities as well. If, if you are going to give the other people, you know, from the other backgrounds, the job opportunities, the volunteering opportunities, then I think in this way you can involve the other people."

The resident emphasised the importance of visible representation.

- **!** The presence of people who they share a language, ethnic, or cultural background with makes residents more willing to engage. Visible representation is a key takeaway for making the GSC Community Hub feel welcoming and inclusive, as

demonstrable through what types of volunteers are present, who attends events, and who is in charge of events. Especially if the hub is intended as a venue of advocacy for the community.

- General Manager Michelle Evans is looking to access funding for an Integration Programme to address these issues and ensure visible representation is apparent.

3.2.2.4. Barriers & Supports for Participation

Several participants expressed interest in participating in initiatives, volunteering, or leading activities, whether for themselves, their children, or others; demonstrating goodwill and a desire to contribute. Participation was seen as rewarding, but residents identified financial barriers, limited time, caring responsibilities, mobility challenges due to health, and lack of convenient transport as obstacles.

- Although recruiting representatives and volunteers, or encouraging the public to participate can feel frustrating, low engagement should not be assumed as disinterest or unwillingness. Such bad faith assumptions can obscure hidden barriers, and may unintentionally reinforce cycles of negative attribution, exclusion, and systemic discrimination.
- One volunteer praised the value of Holiday Hope Camp 2025, which provided childcare and freed them to contribute to community work during the summer holidays.
- Pick-up services for residents with mobility or transport issues were suggested. Weekday Wow Factor, a charity supporting people aged 50+, already provides this service, showing that the hub can host organisations offering such support, rather than providing all services directly.

English proficiency also emerged as a barrier to participating in the community. Figure 5 shows that 10.3% of residents reported a language other than English, Scots, British Sign Language or Gaelic as their main language. Without English fluency, residents may face difficulty in advocating for their rights or in raising concerns, increasing their vulnerability.

- To address this, GSC Auldhouse Foundation hosts free ESOL classes by Glasgow Life, for all ability levels.
- Hosting an organisation like Voiceover by Govan Community Project, who deliver high quality and cost-effective interpreting, translating, and proofreading services for help in navigating bureaucracy and paperwork.

3.2.2.5. Building Trust & Gradual Involvement

Building trust is also key in attracting public engagement, volunteers, and representatives.

As one participant from a charity advised:

- "... if it's a new thing in the area, they'll be kind of wary. It, it takes people in this area a long time to warm up to new faces, and new surroundings."
- Others linked this wariness to past experiences with organisations, where the way residents were treated felt unhelpful or dismissive: "A lot of negative experience." Another member commented, "Yeah, they do have that history where they're very wary. So I would go in fun and cheery." But someone else humorously added, "No promises though!" recognising that overcoming distrust is not immediate, nor guaranteed, and requires ongoing effort. Emphasising the need for understanding and patience.

Trust can be built by offering tangible benefits:

- "Offer things to them though, like say, oh come to this. There'll be bouncy castles. There'll be burgers, you know what I mean? Because people in the community, they go because they're getting something, if that makes sense? Quite a lot of the time."
- They continued to emphasise the strong appeal of food as a reliable incentive: "Yeah, especially if it's a free meal because of no money."
- "They're very underprivileged in this area and they're very deprived of things. They will actively look for things to benefit them and benefit their children. So if you are having- A good thing to do is during the summer holidays because there's not a lot to be done during the summer holidays here." Another added, "Have things that they can kind of sit back and let their kids enjoy."

In summary, engagement and trust build when residents are offered tangible benefits, such as food, family activities, or childcare during summer holidays. These reduce immediate burdens, including food insecurity and caring responsibilities, while providing residents with meaningful social activities. At the same time, they create space for residents to connect, feel included, and familiarise themselves with the opportunities and services available, freeing up time and capacity for participation, whether as continued service users or active volunteers. The charity volunteers noted that some of them began as service users and gradually took on responsibilities, showing that active involvement can develop over time once capacity is freed.

- Asking people from underrepresented backgrounds to participate without recognition of, and assistance in lowering, hidden barriers reduces accessibility and thus engagement. Tokenistic and passive efforts are unhelpful in freeing their capacity to engage. Organisations like the hub or community councils would benefit from considering this to successfully recruit representatives, volunteers, and increase public engagement.
- The hub can offer events with built-in childcare or food to connect residents to community councils or services like the police, particularly during summer holidays. For example, Pollokshaws Community Hub hosted a family-friendly event, with an open side room for the Pollokshaws & Eastwood Community Council. Food and childcare freed residents' capacity, allowing them to engage with and observe the community council in action, thereby building trust. This setup attracted broad attendance, gathered a large volume of community input for the council, and increased public awareness of them.

Overall, the participants emphasise that building trust and capacity is essential before expecting active participation.

- Organisations must demonstrate respect, consistency, and cultural sensitivity to resolve historical mistrust and foster inclusion. Engagement comes after being considered, cared for and thus made to feel wanted and valued. This is a key takeaway for building residents' confidence in the hub, and in themselves, so they can confidently open up and participate.

3.2.3. Advice, Rights, & Community Support

Participants emphasised the value of access to experts through drop-in or booked sessions, to help residents navigate bureaucracy, understand their rights, and advocate for themselves, particularly on legal, housing, and benefits matters. This support is especially important as many Ward 2 neighbourhoods, particularly Carnwadric and Arden, rank among Scotland's most deprived areas according to the SIMD index. Residents also highlighted widespread housing issues, including mould, poor sound insulation, leakages, and general maintenance problems.

- The hub could host advisors from Wheatley Homes or Glen Oaks Housing Association to provide residents with guidance on housing issues, tenancy rights, property maintenance, and access to community support and local services. Both are among the largest and most established housing providers in Ward 2.
- Access to third-party advice may be valuable, as the housing issues involve properties mismanaged by Wheatley Homes or Glen Oaks Housing Association, creating a potential conflict of interest.
- Collaboration with Glasgow Open (GO) Justice centre: provides legal education and community support, helping residents understand their civil rights and navigate legal, housing, and benefits issues.
- Collaboration with VOICES Network: A UK-wide network of refugees and asylum seekers that enables participants to influence policy, and raise awareness of issues affecting displaced communities. Local residents can apply to be VOICES Ambassadors to receive training and support to represent refugee perspectives at national forums.
- Collaboration with Scottish Inter-cultural Association (SIA): promotes intercultural understanding and supports the integration of migrants, refugees, and ethnic minorities in Scotland. They organise community events, workshops, and networking opportunities to foster social inclusion and cultural exchange. Past initiatives include the Kelvingrove Community Friendship BBQ, held as part of Refugee Festival Scotland, which brought together people of different backgrounds through music, poetry, and food.

- Community Links Practitioners with Health & Social Care Alliance Scotland support residents, including asylum seekers and people with mental health needs, by connecting them to relevant local services. The hub can be a nexus and thus help alleviate pressure on existing services like this.
- The hub can raise awareness of available help through hosting family-friendly events in tandem with the presence of support services (e.g. police, community councils, mental health services, etc.) and thus strengthen community ties, resilience and support self-advocacy. Fun, accessible activities can attract residents and provide opportunities to connect them with resources, services, and information.

3.3. Community Environment

3.3.1. Gaps in Local Infrastructure

Participants raised concerns about the local environment, highlighting gaps in amenities and issues in public spaces. Regeneration in Pollokshaws has been ongoing since the masterplan was completed by Anderson Bell & Christie Architects in 2013. As detailed in the Pollokshaws & Eastwood Community Council consultation (PECC, 2024), this process has involved the demolition of housing and the shopping arcade alongside the gradual construction of new residential areas. The prolonged process has left residents in limbo, resulting in widespread derelict buildings and a decline in local shops as businesses close or relocate without replacement, contributing to wider socioeconomic decline. Participants also noted a similar lack of shops, jobs, and services in neighbourhoods immediately surrounding GSC Auldhouse.

The PECC consultation reports strong community demand for communal spaces, independent businesses, and accessible outdoor areas; a view echoed in other parts of Ward 2.

- The GSC Community Hub can work alongside Pollokshaws Community Hub, PECC, and other local organisations, acting as a focal point to address urgent community needs, easing pressure on existing services, while advocating for longer-term solutions.

- General Manager Michelle Evans has actively engaged with local charities, organisations, community councils, and residents to foster collaboration, avoid duplication of services (for example, youth activities like Friday Night Football), and prevent clashes between initiatives. By coordinating efforts and breaking down silos, the hub is growing as a central point to bring together people, information, and resources.

Participants frequently suggested a potential one-way drive system in the GSC Auldhouse neighbourhood, which has been investigated by PECC. At a PECC meeting, a Glasgow City Council representative explained that the one-way system requires unanimous community consent to initiate the council approval process, which itself takes at least a year, in addition to the time necessary for implementation. This extended timeline is deliberate by the council, to ensure residents fully consider and agree to the proposed changes, reducing the risk of later reversals.

Participants raised further infrastructural concerns: limited parking around GSC Auldhouse; the need for a zebra crossing near the Hutchisons Playing Fields bus stops; recurring large puddles; and the slope leading down to GSC Auldhouse posing a challenge for residents with mobility issues.

Participants said shops are few and far between, contributing to food insecurity, noting that supermarkets are only easily accessible by car, and there are no direct public transport routes. Residents without a car must make substantial trips for grocery shopping, often relying on the notoriously unreliable Glasgow bus system and walking. This creates difficulties for residents with mobility challenges.

- One older participant recalled relying on neighbours for shopping when they needed help due to caring responsibilities, highlighting the value of informal support. In response, another participant suggested hosting a volunteer group at the hub to assist local residents with prescription pick-ups, grocery shopping, and other practical support.

- The proposed infrastructural changes fall under the jurisdiction of community councils, Glasgow City Council, and other government bodies; the hub itself does not have any authority in enacting the changes. However, the hub hosts bi-monthly PECC meetings, giving residents a forum to build consensus on the one-way drive system and advocate for similar local infrastructural improvements.

3.3.2. Revitalising Public & Green Spaces

Participants consistently raised concerns about the maintenance and safety of parks and playgrounds. Key issues included: broken glass found in and near playgrounds and outside Eastwood Nursery School; risk of ticks and other pests in neglected long grass; fly-tipping, littering, and dog fouling as environmental and health hazards.

Residents expressed helplessness and frustration at the lack of collective ownership for public cleanliness and safety. They showed embarrassment and concern at the mess seen by visitors:

- "... we have got little ones. So we are worried about them when they go to play to around the corner park. There are lots of broken glasses there which we don't like. Playing places for the children should be kept clean. So we have just been through a big pandemic and what we learned is just hygiene and cleanliness. ... And we are being judged for this."
- "... I had to pick all that stuff. Although it doesn't belong to me, but just to keep the things you know. Tidy. ... But I think people should know themselves. ... It's not only me. It's not only her. It needs to be done with everybody. Everybody."
- "... it doesn't look nice. Other people come to our houses. We don't want to give that kind of image to other people, that the people living in the flats they are just dirty themselves ... Because people can be judgmental by looking at the side- of outside their houses ... So it needs to be clean in that way. And when it comes to the dogs, then obviously the other people has got the dogs ... the English people and we don't have the dogs. Mostly we don't have the dogs and they are not taking the responsibility as she has just mentioned ... of picking [their dog's poop] up ... and it makes the streets dirty. Somebody can just step on it because it's always raining and

we don't know that- What kind of, you know, shoes we are just taking into our houses."

Parks and playgrounds have been neglected, despite their importance as third spaces for social interaction and physical activity. The reduced safe play opportunities for children has discouraged outdoor activity, and fuelled parental concerns about excessive time spent indoors and in front of screens.

- A resident suggested using neglected green spaces for festivals, fairs, and other community events, noting that planned activities can incentivise prompt maintenance. They recalled an instance where grass was cut specifically so a space could be used for a football fundraiser.

Community councils and the Glasgow City Council are aware of this. There are ongoing efforts at a large scale to recruit more waste collection and parks/land services staff within the next year (2025) or so to improve the hygiene and maintenance of public green spaces.

- To foster collective ownership and pride in the community's appearance, a participant suggested a window-box flower competition.
- Dog fouling awareness campaigns and advocating through community councils for additional bins.
- The hub can sign-post residents to PECC's newsletter, which provides information on ways to raise concerns; including but not limited to reporting fly-tipping, and issues with bin collection or parking.
- Glasgow City Council encourages residents to consistently report problems through their apps or website so that problems are tracked and documented. Problems that are not reported are unlikely to be addressed; while persistent, well-documented issues are more likely to be prioritised. It is important residents are made aware of this.
- Residents repeatedly proposed a community clean-up initiative. Pollokshaw Community Hub's clean-up group recommended the Neighbourhood Improvement Volunteer (NIV) Programme, which supplies free equipment such as hi-vis vests, litter pickers, gloves, and bag holders for such initiatives. They also offered a taster

session and to lend equipment to any budding clean-up group based at GSC Auldhouse before an application to NIV is made.

- 💡 Linking recruitment for the clean-up initiative with social activities, such as neighbourhood potlucks, was suggested to sustain participation.
- ⚠️ Efforts to set up a potluck and clean-up initiative at GSC Auldhouse were thwarted due to the unavailability of the premises, as there were an insufficient number of caretakers available to supervise site usage.

There was also great demand by residents for gardening opportunities. Local gardens, such as the Mansewood allotments, have waiting lists exceeding ten years, underlining the need for alternative solutions.

- 💡 Participants suggested smaller-scale gardening initiatives at the hub, by using raised beds, planter boxes, or container gardens, to provide accessible gardening opportunities for residents and maximise use of available space. Strikingly, Pollokshaws Community Hub was born from the humble beginnings of a few residents planting raised beds and planter boxes outside a derelict nursery building. This small gardening initiative gradually gained traction, growing into a fully active community hub.
- 💡 Participants pointed out that gardening could foster intergenerational connections, provide opportunities for teaching and sharing skills, help alleviate food insecurity, and promote a sense of ownership and pride in the community.

Several organisations, including Eastwood Nursery School and the WIN Project, expressed strong interest in using the extensive outdoor space at GSC Auldhouse as one of the few manicured and maintained areas available locally.

- 💡 Hosting summer fun festivals with bouncy castles, face painting, stalls, and activities were suggested.
- 💡 Easter egg hunts, and general use of the outdoor premises for holiday events.
- 💡 Hiring of the building and outdoor spaces for staff training by Eastwood Nursery School or other organisations.
- 💡 WIN Project hosting outdoor BBQs at GSC Auldhouse.

- Potential conflicts were noted between community use and club requirements for pitches, including concerns about income generation and damage to the pitches.

3.4. Safety & Anti-Social Behaviour

Key issues reported, but not limited to, included: vandalism of Eastwood Nursery School; children playing on roofs; youth playing loud music in residential areas at night; youth antisocial behaviour, some as young as 8-12 years; incidences of playground structures being set on fire; knife crime; verbal abuse, racism and hate crimes; and frequent instances of domestic abuse.

- A charity volunteer suggested having a "wall of leaflets" at the hub to discreetly signpost residents to different support services. They particularly noted the need for sexual health and family planning guidance.

Residents frequently identified a lack of safe, supervised activities for children, due to a drop in the number of available opportunities. Historically, there was the 50p Church where kids could go get a juice box and play pool, but that is no longer being offered. Those with access to cars may travel further away for opportunities or afford more expensive local options, but local children have few cheap/free options nearby other than staying indoors on screens or loitering in neglected playgrounds and parks. Residents note that this contributes to anti-social behaviour and the formation of gangs. Volunteers from a charity described some children as being caught between unsafe home environments and unsafe streets, highlighting the need for a safe third space.

- Several residents fondly recalled the 50p Church and the difference it made in their lives. They suggested that the hub could implement similar low-cost or free activities to keep young people off the streets and away from drinking or drugs.
- Preventive measures, such as early engagement police programmes like "Pitchin' In" and other youth-focused initiatives, are essential for addressing issues before they escalate, and alleviating pressure on services further down the line.
- The hub is acting as a link between the police and the community. Officers are invited to work with young people attending Friday Night Football to build trust,

educate them on discrimination and substance abuse in addition to other issues, and encourage positive community involvement.

- The hub is collaborating with Aberlour Children's Charity, who operates the Youthpoint service, targeting areas with high levels of social deprivation, crime, and gang culture. Key services include detached street work, harm reduction, conflict resolution, and volunteer training. The approach focuses on building relationships and promoting citizenship to divert young people from negative influences.
- Police resources are limited, so officers at a PECC meeting stressed the importance of consistently reporting incidents. Well-documented patterns of crime at one location are prioritised to triage resources effectively.
- While there is a distinct lack of opportunities for kids, some participants pointed out that there is even less so for older teens and adults in general, that does not revolve around drinking.

3.5. Youth Engagement & Activities

Popular suggestions included:

- Mathnasium, an organisation who used STEM activities to teach children the fun side of maths, was involved in Holiday Hope Camp 2025.
- The Army's Regional Engagement Team Scotland, took the children through team building and resilience activities in Holiday Hope Camp 2025.
- Mums & bumps or toddler groups, Bookbug, and etc. To offer peer support for parents and young children at the hub, building a community safety net.
- Physical exercise classes, such as yoga, dance or aerobics.
- Due to widespread concern over children spending excessive time indoors and in front of screens, there is strong demand for outdoor social activities, particularly during summer holidays and other school breaks.
- After-school or homework clubs, to offer guardians childcare, and the children activities during term time.
- Hosting sports activities at GSC Auldhouse, to take advantage of its large outdoor space, and collaborating with schools and other organisations to provide accessible sports opportunities.

- A volunteer recommended that children should be asked what they want and allowed to lead activities to build confidence and autonomy. Ideally, they should be able to take ownership of a space and be encouraged to personalise it.
- General Manager Michelle Evans has submitted a bid to the Glasgow Communities Fund to host a Youth Hub on Friday and Saturday nights. The outcome will be announced in November 2025. If approved, it would be a three-year programme, giving children and young people the opportunity to shape its activities.

3.6. Education & Skills Gaps

Participants suggested:

- Volunteering opportunities for teens, adults, and older community members to gain experience, training, and demonstrate reliability for future employment. Apart from fostering a sense of purpose, wellbeing and belonging, there are awards like the Duke of Edinburgh or Saltire that recognise volunteering efforts. Completing the Gold Duke of Edinburgh Award prior to higher education applications offers UCAS points.
- At the time of writing, the hub is offering volunteering opportunities in the café. The hub also seeks volunteers to help run a Sporting Memories Group, with training provided, and has already recruited two local residents to lead the group. The Sporting Memories Group uses sports-related conversation, games, and activities to support older adults, particularly those living with dementia, depression, or loneliness.
- Collaboration with KWETU Café, which provides free barista training for refugees and asylum seekers.
- Signposting to or collaborating with the Glasgow Trust project. They support vulnerable and care-experienced young people by providing housing, education, training, and employability assistance, helping them achieve stability, skills development, and long-term wellbeing.
- The hub collaborated with local organisations like Carnwadric WIN Project, Auldhouse Community Foodbank and Glenoaks Housing Association who referred children and families in their network most in need to Holiday Hope Camp 2025. The

WIN Project is a key collaborator, located nearby and offering a wide range of family-focused support and activities, including but not limited to ASN-focused groups, "Chat & Chill" sessions, BBQs, and back-to-school haircuts.

- Signposting to job-hunting sites and resources, such as: Planet Plus (for local jobs and CV building); My World of Work website (CVs, career guidance); One Jobs Scotland; Indeed; and national careers service (booking appointments with their careers advisors for CV writing or other help).
- The hub collaborated with WorkingRite to offer a placement to a young trainee caretaker at the premises. The aim is to provide a successful placement that could lead to a full-time role. WorkingRite supports young people aged 15-25 in Glasgow by providing work experience, mentoring, and skills development to help them transition into sustainable employment.
- A frequent suggestion was life skills workshops for children, especially cooking classes. Participants showed interest in a cultural exchange of recipes.

3.7. Social Isolation

Barriers to community participation contribute to social isolation. One resident described having to stop leading their Girl's Brigade unit due to caring responsibilities, and being left in isolated limbo because of multi-year waiting lists for whatever limited support services was available to them. Similarly, a mental health care provider noted understaffing, explaining that by the time people reach them, limited funding, time, and personnel mean their capacity is focused on "putting out fires" rather than fully resolving issues.

Targeted groups can lower barriers by providing safe, trusted and reliable spaces where members share similar experiences and identities. These in-groups can serve as immediate peer support networks, providing prompt support compared to services with long waiting lists and helping participants find belonging.

- Some participants noted that stigma may make individuals reluctant to join visibly labelled support groups. For example, people may avoid support groups openly labelled for issues like domestic abuse, but they may open up about such issues as a natural consequence of getting to know other parents or volunteers during family-

oriented activities. However, those who need a particular support group may struggle to find it without visible labelling.

- Participants recommended signposting targeted support groups through GPs and health practitioners; using word-of-mouth and referrals rather than visible public signposting.
- Participants suggested offering support indirectly, for example through food, childcare, and a warm space to sit and chat. They said this approach helps build trust naturally, making people more likely to confide and accept help or referrals.
- Participants suggested offering simultaneous activities: one for children and one for parents/carers. This lets carers use the time freed from childcare to connect and build peer networks with other carers.
- Providing free, regular meals, in addition to occasional potlucks and BBQs, was strongly recommended as the best way to gather the community together.
- Participants suggested providing a warm space in winter to shelter in. Pollokshaws Community Hub has had particular success with providing "warm boxes" (packages containing blankets, hats, gloves, etc. made by their crafts group) and a hardship fund during winter.

Particular groups that may benefit from being specifically catered to include:

- Neurodivergent folks. For example, General Manager Michelle Evans attended training on inclusivity for neurodivergent individuals and has deliberately designed activities with routine (same people, time, location), and chosen quiet periods to reduce sensory overwhelm.
- LGBTQIA+ clubs for youth or adults. For example, Glasgow Frontrunners is an award-winning, inclusive, community-based running club for LGBT+ people and allies. Similarly, the hub could host football sessions, board game nights, etc. that are specifically for LGBT+ folk. Or collaborate with existing organisations like Time for Inclusive Education (educational workshops), Saltire Thistle FC, or LEAP Sports Scotland (free sports activities and support, like Pride Youth Games).

- Initiatives targeted at girls or women. For example, This Girl Can (campaign to encourage women and girls of all ages, abilities, and backgrounds to engage in physical activity), Girls' Brigade, or Girlguiding. Collaboration with Glasgow City FC.
- Initiatives targeted at asylum seekers or immigrants. Collaboration with VOICES (advocating for rights), KWETU (barista training for refugees and asylum seekers), Scottish Inter-cultural Association (cultural exchange events), or United Glasgow FC (for displaced youth).
- Initiatives targeted at men's mental health. Pollokshaws Community Hub has seen particular success with setting up their own Men's Sheds group. The group offers a space for men who are retired, unemployed, or facing health challenges to participate in social activities like woodwork, or gardening.
- Initiatives targeted at older residents. Collaborating with Age Scotland, Weekday Wow Factor (activities for those aged 50+), or Rainbow Friendship Centre. Alternatively, activities like crafts (crochet, knitting, etc.), yoga, Tai Chi, bingo, social dancing, walking groups, walking football (already being offered at GSC Auldhouse), mobility fitness classes, or quiet reflection space (for quiet reflection, prayer, or remembering deceased loved ones).

3.8. Staffing & Logistics

3.8.1. Staffing Needs

As mentioned previously, the hub is currently heavily understaffed and requires funding to fill those roles.

- Most urgently needed are a Programme Manager/Coordinator, Volunteer Coordinator, Youth Workers, and Sports Coaches to ensure the smooth and consistent running of activities and programmes. Securing funding for these roles is vital, as it is neither sustainable nor feasible for General Manager Michelle Evans to continue carrying the wide range of duties required to establish and operate the hub. These roles form the foundation necessary to run and maintain programmes effectively at the hub.
- The hub needs enough caretakers to cover day, night, and weekend shifts. Without sufficient caretakers, use of the premises is limited and there are security

and safeguarding risks, as people have been known to enter the premises unsupervised. Relying on other staff to cover the shortage of caretakers is not practical, as janitorial duties, fire warden responsibilities, and other caretaking tasks fall outside their roles. The shortage has also prevented hiring of the premises and left it underused during the day, wasting heating and electricity and missing opportunities for community use and income generation. At least three trained caretakers are needed to ensure safe and consistent operations. To address this, the hub has partnered with WorkingRite to place a trainee caretaker on site. This placement is intended to resolve the immediate issue and, if successful, could lead to a permanent role, providing a sustainable solution to the caretaker shortage.

3.8.2. Volunteers

Volunteers can be recruited through two main approaches:

- Recruitment within the community to help secure volunteers who are locally invested. School networks, particularly teenagers completing their Duke of Edinburgh awards, may provide the most readily available pool of volunteers, provided the hub is an approved activity provider. Ward 2 has a population of 24,392 (Brinkhoff, 2024), and only a fraction of this population would be aware of GSC Auldhouse, available, and interested in volunteering.
- Previous recruitment of local volunteers has been successful. A local volunteer kindly helped prepare lunch at Holiday Hope Camp 2025, two local residents will assist with running the Sporting Memories Group at the hub, and two teenagers are helping at Friday Night Football as part of their Duke of Edinburgh award.
- Recruitment outside the community. For example, through the Saltire awards, the Duke of Edinburgh awards, or universities which often have active volunteering drives. These organisations provide access to much larger pools of people who are more readily available and interested in volunteering than the available local population. SRC Volunteering alone gives access to the University of Glasgow's 35,000+ students, which surpasses Ward 2's population size. Additionally, these organisations have active online databases for the hub to advertise vacancies in,

which makes recruitment more convenient. The population of student volunteers may also be already trained in desired skills like marketing.

In order to retain volunteers long-term and reduce turnover, inspiration can be drawn from the very successful example of the WIN Project:

- 💡 Employability upskilling for their volunteers, such as food hygiene certification, first aid, safeguarding, and Bookbug training.
- 💡 Deliberate appreciation for volunteers shown by organising social outings, such as outdoor trips. This recognises that part of the incentive for volunteering is socialisation and a sense of belonging, so space and time must be dedicated team bonding. Treating volunteers simply as work horses might cause disengagement and dropout.
- 💡 Some volunteers began as service users, which builds credibility and trust, as they serve as living examples of the organisation's success.

3.8.3. Access

There is limited parking in and surrounding the GSC Auldhouse premises to cope with large volumes of traffic.

- ✅ Courtesy of General Manager Michelle Evans and Groundskeeper Adam Richardson, signage has been put up to discourage visitors from parking in the immediate local neighbourhood. Michelle has engaged extensively with locals and the PECC to address concerns regarding the parking issues and related antisocial behaviour.
- ⚠️ However, visitors continue to break rules, and there have been instances of verbal abusive directed at local residents.
- 💡 Michelle suggests a satellite parking area with a shuttle service to GSC Auldhouse for major events, such as the festival. This would provide access to the premises during large events while minimising repeated disruption to the local community.

3.8.4. Outreach

Community outreach campaigns are essential to raise awareness of GSC Community Hub, increase engagement, and maximise impact.

- Key recommended points of dissemination included: posters in local shops; referral services like healthcare providers, GPs, the police (Tanya Honeyman), community councils, Glasgow City Council (Jim Kane), Glasgow Life; other charities like the WIN Project, and Pollokshaws Community Hub; and school networks (Tanya Honeyman, or the headteacher at Eastwood Nursery School).
- Participants highlighted the importance of using multiple advertising mediums to reach all parts of the community, such as laminated posters attached to lamp posts, leaflets delivered to homes, and social media (in particular the various neighbourhood Facebook pages).
- Improved signage, both leading to and within the GSC Auldhouse premises, is needed to help find the hub and navigate the premises. Internal signage should also make the hub presence more visible in GSC Auldhouse, particularly as the space is currently dominated by football branding.
- A noticeboard and monthly newsletter were suggested by residents to keep the community in the loop on news from the hub. Existing newsletters, like PECC's or the school networks', can be also used.

3.9. Funding

3.9.1. Opportunities

A staff member at another charity described challenges in accessing financial administration support as a small organisation. Despite having more direct and immediate local impact in comparison to larger charities, by nature of being a small grassroots charity, they were denied support for being too small. Which ironically meant being stuck in a catch-22 where they could not grow without support, yet could not qualify for it. Additionally, they mentioned competition between existing services for the same pool of funding, further limiting the survival and growth of grassroots initiatives. This may partly explain why the provision of local services has declined, despite ongoing community demand.

- 💡 Participants showed interest in contributing towards bake sales, as part of larger events hosted by the hub to fundraise. Another resident suggested raffles.
- 💡 A participant advised involving local businesses as a means of getting donations and funding. In particular, rather than competing, involving the businesses in the hub's activities. For example, inviting the local café to operate the café inside GSC Auldhouse.

In the spirit of collaboration and sharing knowledge, the following is a (non-exhaustive) list of public funding sources. In recognition that, while organisations may compete for funding, we are ultimately working toward the same community goals, and working in isolation goes counter to that. Thank you to those who contributed towards this list:

- 💡 A database of funding sources: <https://funding.scot/>
- ✅ Foundation Scotland, Nourish the Nation (led by Sainsbury's in partnership with Comic Relief), and Cash For Kids funded Holiday Hope Camp 2025.
- 💡 Active Glasgow Community Fund.
- 💡 Active Glasgow Volunteer Fund.
- 💡 Avondale.
- 💡 Celtic FC Foundation.
- 💡 Glasgow City Council's Area Partnership budgets. In particular the Ward 2 annual budget, but perhaps the Ward 3 budget as well if the hub attracts residents from those areas. The Delegated Functions allow more immediate funds of up to £500 (e.g. providing snacks and water for an activity), but requires receipts, a bank account and a clear demonstration of benefits to local residents. The Standard Applications take longer and allow fundings of up to £8,000.
- 💡 Glasgow City Foundation.
- 💡 Glasgow Communities Fund.
- 💡 Housing associations' community funding. In particular, projects that support Wheatley and Glen Oaks Housing Association tenants and the wider community.
- 💡 LEAP Sports Scotland.
- 💡 National Lottery.

- 💡 Police Scotland's community engagement fund.
- 💡 Rangers Charity Foundation.
- 💡 Scottish Football Association.
- 💡 Scottish Football Partnership.
- 💡 Scottish Landfill Communities Fund.
- 💡 Show Racism the Red Card campaign.
- 💡 Social Investment Scotland.
- 💡 sportscotland.
- 💡 Supermarket community funding. For example, Tesco Community Grants, Morrisons Foundation, and Nourish the Nation (led by Sainsbury's in partnership with Comic Relief).
- 💡 University of Glasgow's Find a Solution programme.
- 💡 Ward Discretionary Funds.

Advice given by key participants experienced in fundraising:

- 💡 Speak the language of the funders. Use terminology and buzz words like "holiday hunger".
- 💡 Show a record of successfully running events, raising funds, and collect evidence to demonstrate impact. Pollokshaws Community Hub, for example, collects regular feedback on the impact their activities have on people's sense of wellbeing and health.

3.9.2. Feedback & Assessing Impact

For continuous improvement and to ensure hub users and the wider community are listened to, regular feedback should be collected. Managing this process would be a key responsibility of the hub's administrator/coordinator.

- 💡 To encourage honesty and participation, feedback should be gathered anonymously, either through a suggestion box in a low-traffic area or online, and monitored regularly.

- Findings should be regularly reported publicly in an accessible format, showing “here’s what you said” and “here’s what we did,” to identify action points, obstacles, and current progress. Depending on how responsive the hub wants to be to feedback, "regularly" can mean anywhere between monthly, quarterly or annually.

4. Results Section Summaries

4.1. Poverty & Basic Needs

- Socioeconomic Deprivation (SIMD)
 - Target outreach and programs to Carnwadric and Arden due to need and proximity.
- Affordability
 - Offering free or low-cost programs requires funding (Friday Night Football, Holiday Hope Camp 2025).
 - Introduce postcode-based discounts for venue hire.
 - Understaffing is a key barrier; Programme Manager/Coordinator, Volunteer Coordinator, Youth Workers, Sports Coaches, and etc. are needed.
- Food Insecurity
 - Establish a community foodbank or pantry.
 - Provide discreet access: home delivery, scheduled pick-ups, “take what you need” trolleys.
 - Learn from Helping Hands and Auldhouse Community Foodbanks, and acquire donations through supermarkets.
- Community Resource Sharing
 - Set up donation or swap systems for clothes, toys, books, household items.
 - Introduce tool library or Repair Café for skills sharing.
 - Collaborate with schools and charities for joint initiatives.

4.2. Cultural Integration & Inclusivity

- Racism & Discrimination
 - Immigrant and ethnic minority residents face racism: stereotyping, colourism, hate crimes and microaggressions. They also face barriers: language, bureaucracy, and social isolation.
 - Residents are targeted for superficial visible differences, affecting social integration and wellbeing.

- Host shared activities, cultural exchange events, and inclusive play opportunities to reduce prejudice and promote familiarity e.g. funding for an Integration Programme.
- Community Engagement & Inclusion
 - Community Council meetings often see low public attendance.
 - Social clusters along ethnic, cultural, or religious lines limit broader community participation.
 - Tailor events to dietary, faith, and cultural needs to increase inclusivity.
 - Recruit representatives from underrepresented groups to improve engagement and advocacy.
- Barriers to Participation
 - Financial constraints, time pressures, caring responsibilities, mobility issues, and lack of transport limit engagement.
 - English proficiency can restrict self-advocacy and utilisation of services.
 - Build trust gradually; offer tangible benefits such as childcare, food, or family-friendly activities.
 - Provide ESOL classes and interpretation/translation services.
 - Pick-up services can support residents with mobility or transport issues.
- Advice, Rights & Community Support
 - Residents need access to experts for legal, housing, and benefits advice.
 - Wheatley Homes and Glen Oaks Housing Association offer advisors. But third-party advice may be necessary due to conflict of interest their advice presents.
 - Partner with organisations such as Glasgow Open Justice, VOICES Network, SIA, and Health & Social Care Alliance Scotland to improve advocacy, intercultural integration, and access to resources.
 - Raise awareness through family-friendly events to link residents to services and support networks.

4.3. Community Environment

- Gaps in Local Infrastructure

- Residents report lack of shops, services, and jobs around GSC Auldhouse.
- Derelict buildings and ongoing regeneration contribute to socioeconomic decline.
- Issues include limited parking, need for zebra crossings, recurrent large puddles, and a steep slope leading to GSC Auldhouse affecting accessibility.
- GSC Hub can collaborate with Pollokshaws Community Hub, PECC, and local organisations to address urgent needs and coordinate longer-term initiatives.
- A volunteer group could assist residents with grocery shopping, prescription pick-ups, and other practical support.
- Bi-monthly PECC meetings at the hub allow residents to advocate for long-term infrastructural improvements.
- Revitalising Public & Green Spaces
 - Parks and playgrounds face maintenance issues: broken glass, long grass, pests, fly-tipping, littering, and dog fouling.
 - Lack of collective ownership reduces community pride and discourages outdoor activity.
 - Suggested initiatives: window-box flower competitions, dog fouling awareness campaigns, community clean-ups, linking clean-ups with social events for volunteer recruitment.
 - The Neighbourhood Improvement Volunteer programme offers free equipment for voluntary clean-up groups.
 - Insufficient number of caretakers prevented the hub from hosting a clean-up group.
- Gardening & Community Events
 - Long waiting lists for Mansewood allotments highlight demand for gardening opportunities.
 - Hub could implement small-scale gardening (raised beds, planter boxes, container gardens) to foster intergenerational connections, and community pride.
 - Outdoor premises can host festivals, fairs, summer events, Easter activities, BBQs, and staff training for partner organisations.

- Potential conflicts exist between community use and club requirements for pitches, including income and maintenance concerns.

4.4. Safety & Anti-Social Behaviour

- Key issues
 - Vandalism, unsafe play, youth antisocial behaviour, arson, knife crime, verbal abuse, racism, hate crimes, domestic abuse.
- Safe spaces
 - Lack of supervised activities drives bored children to wander unsafe streets; low-cost/free initiatives like the former 50p Church could provide safe third spaces.
- Interventions
 - Early engagement programmes (“Pitchin’ In”), police collaboration during Friday Night Football, partnership with Youthpoint for street work, harm reduction, and conflict resolution.
 - Consistent incident reporting to police and Glasgow City Council needed to prioritise resources.

4.5. Youth Engagement & Activities

- Programmes
 - STEM and resilience activities (Mathnasium, Army Regional Engagement Team), sports at GSC Auldhouse, outdoor social events during school breaks, and after-school/homework clubs.
- Social support
 - Peer groups for parents and young children to build safety nets; children encouraged to lead activities and personalise spaces to develop ownership and autonomy.

4.6. Education & Skills Gaps

- Volunteering

- Opportunities for teens, adults, and older community members to gain experience, training, and recognition (Duke of Edinburgh, Saltire Awards); hub offers roles in Sporting Memories Group and café.
- Skills development
 - Collaboration with KWETU Café (barista training for refugees/asylum seekers), Glasgow Trust (housing, education, employability support), WorkingRite (mentoring, work experience).
- Life skills
 - Workshops for children, especially cooking, including cultural exchange of recipes; signposting to job resources (Planet Plus, My World of Work, One Jobs Scotland, Indeed, national careers service).

4.7. Social Isolation

- Barriers
 - Caring responsibilities, long waiting lists, understaffed services, and stigma contribute to isolation.
- Peer support
 - Targeted groups provide safe, trusted spaces for shared experiences; simultaneous parent-child activities and warm spaces with food or childcare build trust naturally.
- Targeted initiatives
 - Neurodivergent-friendly activities, LGBTQIA+ clubs, women/girls' groups, asylum seeker/immigrant support, men's mental health groups, and activities for older residents.

4.8. Staffing & Logistics

- Staffing needs
 - Heavily understaffed. Funding required for Programme Manager/Coordinator, Volunteer Coordinator, Youth Workers, Sports Coaches, and etc. Current reliance on General Manager to do everything is unsustainable.

- Insufficient caretakers limit operations, create safety risks, and reduce venue hire opportunities; at least three trained caretakers required. WorkingRite trainee caretaker in placement, with potential permanent role which may resolve issue.
- Volunteers
 - Recruitment can target local residents (schools, Duke of Edinburgh) and external pools (universities, volunteering platforms).
 - Retention strategies include upskilling, and social gratification.
- Access
 - Limited parking and local complaints; temporary signage helps, but long-term solutions could include satellite parking with a shuttle service for major events like festivals.
- Outreach
 - Awareness raised via posters, leaflets, social media, school and healthcare networks; noticeboards, and newsletters recommended to improve visibility and engagement.
 - Internal and external signage for finding hub and navigating it internally.

4.9. Funding

- Opportunities
 - Grassroots charities face barriers: too small to access financial administration support, yet unable to grow without it. Competition for limited funds reduces longevity of local services.
 - Local fundraising options include bake sales, raffles, and involving businesses directly in hub activities.
 - Non-exhaustive but extended list of public funding sources provided.
 - Fundraising strategies should use funder language (e.g. “holiday hunger”) and demonstrate evidence of impact through records of impact and community feedback.
- Feedback & Assessing Impact
 - Anonymous feedback collected via suggestion boxes or online surveys.

- Closing the loop with community feedback by regular reporting (“what you said, what we did”), which can be monthly, quarterly, or annually, and should be overseen by the hub administrator/coordinator.

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6. Appendices

6.1. Appendix A – Participant Information Sheet, For The People

For The People

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

You are invited to take part in our community consultation!

GSC Auldhouse Foundation is creating a new community hub for the people of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area. We want this hub to reflect **your** voice: what you need, what you care about, and what would help you and your loved ones.

So, we are inviting you to share your thoughts and experiences about living in this community, and any suggestions you may have.

Please take a few minutes to read this information carefully. You are welcome to contact us if you have any questions or need help understanding anything.

Who can take part?

We welcome anyone 18 years old or over, who currently lives in the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area.

Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area includes Arden, Kennishead, Carnwadric, Mansewood, Hillpark, Newlands, Muirend, Pollokshaws, and Eastwood. Below is a map of the area:

What will I be asked to do?

You are invited to join a discussion, which will last about one hour and will be guided by our researcher(s).

We will ask you about:

- What life is like in the community
- What challenges you or others face
- What the community needs most
- Your ideas for what could help the community and why
- What would make the new hub feel useful and welcoming
- Suggestions for activities, spaces, or support services in the hub
 - *(By “spaces” we mean what the building or outdoor areas could have: like a prayer room, a quiet space, a breastfeeding space, accessible toilets, or places to sit outside.)*

We will also ask you about some personal information, including:

- Your age group
- How you are connected to the local area
- How long you have lived in Ward 2 (if you currently live here)
- Your gender identity
- Your ethnic background
- Your full name

This personal information helps us to better understand who is taking part and to make sure we hear from a wide range of people.

How will my information be used?

The things you share will help us plan services, activities, and spaces that support the local people. We will include what we learn in a report that will help GSC Auldhouse Foundation apply for funding to pay for these plans.

We will also share this report with the public (such as at community events or online) because it is important to us that the community knows what we found out and how their voices have helped shape the hub.

Your name or personal details will not be shared in the report. The personal information you provide (like age group or how long you've lived in the area) will only be used to create summary statistics. For example:

- “52% of participants were female”
- “40% of participants have lived in Ward 2 for over 5 years”

This means your answers will be combined with others to give an overall picture of our participants, not to identify individuals.

If we include quotes in the report, we will:

- Use a made-up name (pseudonym), such as “Participant A”
- Remove anything specific that could identify you

Example:

- **Participant A said:** “(My daughter) really likes Friday Night Football and has made lots of friends there. I work at (a local business), and Fridays are so busy, so it's nice that I can drop her off there for the evening.”

How will the discussion be recorded and stored?

With your permission, the discussion will be audio recorded using voice recorders. The audio files will then be securely uploaded to a GDPR-compliant, password-protected OneDrive folder. After upload, all audio recordings will be permanently deleted from the voice recorders.

One week after the discussion is held, the stored audio recordings will be typed up (transcribed). Once transcribed, the stored audio recordings will be permanently deleted from OneDrive.

The transcripts will then be used for analysis and writing the report. After the report is done, the transcripts will be permanently deleted (no later than 18:00 Monday, 1st September 2025).

How will my personal information and consent be recorded and stored?

If you decide to take part, we will ask you to fill in hard copies of the Consent Form and a Demographics Form (which asks about personal information such as age or gender identity).

One week after the discussion, the information from the filled-in Demographics Form will be entered into an Excel file and stored in OneDrive. After that, hard copies of the Demographics Forms will be destroyed.

The Excel file will be used to create summary statistics for the report. Then, the Excel file will be permanently deleted (no later than 18:00 Monday, 1st September 2025).

Photocopies of the signed Consent Forms will be stored in OneDrive with no set end date, and the hard copies destroyed. This is because we may need to show, if asked, that you gave permission to take part in the study.

How will the discussion be kept safe?

We take your privacy seriously. To protect your identity, each person who takes part will be given a made-up name (pseudonym), so your real name will not appear in the report. The list that links your real name to your pseudonym will be permanently deleted once we finish typing up the audio recordings (transcribing).

Only Sara Eftekhari and Liz Millard will have access to the audio recordings, transcripts and demographic data. They have both been trained in Data Protection and Information Security through training modules provided by the University of Glasgow.

GSC Auldhouse Foundation will collect, store, and use your data safely, following all relevant data protection policies and regulations, such as GDPR 2018 and the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002.

We have also created formal documents (like Data Management Plans and Legitimate Interest Assessments) to show how we are following these regulations and making careful decisions. These documents, along with the final report, will be the only materials kept after the project ends (no later than 18:00 Monday, 1st September 2025). They will be stored with no set end date.

What if I change my mind?

Taking part is your choice. You can change your mind at any time. Your decision will be respected, and your legal rights will not be affected.

You can leave the discussion at any time. To do this, just tell the researcher(s), and you are free to leave. You do not need to give a specific reason.

After the discussion, you have **seven full days (from the time the discussion ends) to let us know if you want anything you said to be permanently deleted.** This gives you a chance to change your mind before we type up the audio recordings, Demographics Forms and anonymise the transcripts. **After that point, we will not be able to link any of your responses or data back to you, so it will no longer be possible to separate your data from the others' and permanently delete it.**

If you want all of your data to be permanently deleted, **please tell us by email** within those seven days. **If you leave the discussion but do not email us to let us know this, we will keep and use anything you said before you left.**

Are there any risks to taking part?

There is a risk that someone could recognise you from what you say, even if your name is not used. This is called the *mosaic effect* or *triangulation*, which means that small pieces of information can be put together to find out who someone is.

However, this risk is made as small as possible.

We do this by grouping your answers with others', giving you a made-up name (pseudonym), and changing any details in quotes that could show who you are into less specific words. For example, instead of saying "I work at the Bakery on Main Street," we will instead use "I work at (a local business)."

You can choose what you feel comfortable to share during the discussion. If there are other participants present, such as during a group discussion instead of a one-on-one interview, we will also ask everyone to respect each other's privacy and keep what is said private.

Who is running this project?

This project is run by **GSC Auldhouse Foundation**, a local organisation that supports families, young people, and the wider community. It is funded by the **University of Glasgow's Find A Solution 2025 programme.**

The team working on this project includes:

- Sara Eftekhari – Principal Investigator and Community Engagement Research Intern
 - sara@giffnocksoccercentre.com *

- Liz Millard – Research Assistant Volunteer
 - liz@giffnocksoccercentre.com *
- Michelle Evans – General Manager
 - michelle@giffnocksoccercentre.com

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us.

GSC Auldhouse Foundation
180 Thornliebank Rd
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G46 7RQ

* Please note that these email accounts are no longer monitored as of 08/09/2025, following the end of Sara and Liz's contracts.

6.2. Appendix B – Participant Information Sheet, For People Who Look After The People

For People Who Look After The People

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

You are invited to take part in our community consultation!

GSC Auldhouse Foundation is creating a new community hub for the people of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area. We want this hub to reflect **your** voice: what would help the people you care for, and what would support you in caring for them, both personally and professionally.

So we are inviting you to share your thoughts and experiences about supporting the local community, and any suggestions you may have.

Please take a few minutes to read this information carefully. You are welcome to contact us if you have any questions or need help understanding anything.

Who can take part?

We welcome anyone 18 years old or over, who currently lives in the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) community or supports them in any way e.g. through work or volunteering.

Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area includes Arden, Kennishead, Carnwadric, Mansewood, Hillpark, Newlands, Muirend, Pollokshaws, and Eastwood. Below is a map of the area:

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- Your ideas for what could help the community and why
- What would make the new hub feel useful and welcoming
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 - *(By “spaces” we mean what the building or outdoor areas could have: like a prayer room, a quiet space, a breastfeeding space, accessible toilets, or places to sit outside.)*

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- Your age group
- How you are connected to the local area
- How long you have lived in Ward 2 (if you currently live here)
- Your gender identity
- Your ethnic background
- Your full name

This personal information helps us to better understand who is taking part and to make sure we hear from a wide range of people.

How will my information be used?

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You can leave the discussion at any time. To do this, just tell the researcher(s), and you are free to leave. You do not need to give a specific reason.

After the discussion, you have **seven full days (from the time the discussion ends) to let us know if you want anything you said to be permanently deleted.** This gives you a chance to change your mind before we type up the audio recordings, Demographics Forms and anonymise the transcripts. **After that point, we will not be able to link any of your responses or data back to you, so it will no longer be possible to separate your data from the others' and permanently delete it.**

If you want all of your data to be permanently deleted, **please tell us by email** within those seven days. **If you leave the discussion but do not email us to let us know this, we will keep and use anything you said before you left.**

Are there any risks to taking part?

There is a risk that someone could recognise you from what you say, even if your name is not used. This is called the *mosaic effect* or *triangulation*, which means that small pieces of information can be put together to find out who someone is.

However, this risk is made as small as possible.

We do this by grouping your answers with others', giving you a made-up name (pseudonym), and changing any details in quotes that could show who you are into less specific words. For example, instead of saying "I work at the Bakery on Main Street," we will instead use "I work at (a local business)."

You can choose what you feel comfortable to share during the discussion. If there are other participants present, such as during a group discussion instead of a one-on-one interview, we will also ask everyone to respect each other's privacy and keep what is said private.

Who is running this project?

This project is run by **GSC Auldhouse Foundation**, a local organisation that supports families, young people, and the wider community. It is funded by the **University of Glasgow's Find A Solution 2025 programme.**

The team working on this project includes:

- Sara Eftekhari – Principal Investigator and Community Engagement Research Intern
 - sara@giffnocksoccercentre.com *

- Liz Millard – Research Assistant Volunteer
 - liz@giffnocksoccercentre.com *
- Michelle Evans – General Manager
 - michelle@giffnocksoccercentre.com

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us.

GSC Auldhouse Foundation
180 Thornliebank Rd
Thornliebank
Glasgow
G46 7RQ

* Please note that these email accounts are no longer monitored as of 08/09/2025, following the end of Sara and Liz's contracts.

6.3. Appendix C – Privacy Notice

PRIVACY NOTICE

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

GSC Auldhouse Foundation will be what is known as the *Data Controller* (meaning, responsible for the processing) of your personal data during this project titled “**Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub**”. This Privacy Notice will explain how GSC Auldhouse Foundation will process your personal data.

Why we need your personal information:

We will collect some basic details about you, like your age group and gender identity. We use this information only to understand and describe the group of people taking part and to check who can join the discussion (such as only people who are connected to Ward 2). We will not use the information to identify anyone. To protect your privacy, we will collect only the smallest amount of personally identifiable information needed.

Legal basis for processing your data:

As we are a charity working to help the local community, the legal basis we use to process your personal data is **Article 6(1)(f) of UK GDPR**: *"processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child."* If we need to use a different legal basis, like consent, we will explain this clearly in the Consent Form.

What we do with your data and who we share it with:

All the personal information you give us for this project is handled by Sara Eftekhari and Liz Millard, who have signed confidentiality agreements with GSC Auldhouse Foundation. During the project and while the data is stored, all information will be kept safe on auto-encrypted and password-protected servers. Unless you agree to share your data publicly, it will never be sent outside the UK.

How long do we keep your data for:

The report, which only includes summarised and anonymised information, and photocopies of the Consent Forms will be kept by GSC Auldhouse Foundation for archiving. They will be stored on a OneDrive account linked to Michelle Evans with no set end date. When Michelle leaves her role, they will either be permanently deleted or passed on to her replacement as part of the handover.

Your audio recordings will be permanently deleted once they have been transcribed and anonymised seven full days (at earliest) after the discussion you attended, and the transcripts will be permanently deleted when the report is finished, no later than 18:00 on Monday, 1st September 2025.

Hard copies of your Demographics Form will be destroyed once typed up seven full days (at earliest) after the discussion you attended, and the digital demographic data will be permanently deleted once summary statistics has been calculated for the report, no later than 18:00 on Monday, 1st September 2025.

What are your rights?

Please note that your ability to use these rights depends on the legal basis we use to process your data.

Under the UK GDPR, you have the following rights:

- to obtain access to, and copies of, the personal data that we hold about you;
- to require that we cease processing your personal data if the processing is causing you damage or distress;
- to require us to correct the personal data we hold about you if it is incorrect;
- to require us to erase your personal data;
- to require us to restrict our data processing activities;
- to receive from us the personal data we hold about you, which you have provided to us, in a reasonable format specified by you, including for the purpose of you transmitting that personal data to another data controller;
- to object, on grounds relating to your particular situation, to any of our particular processing activities where you feel this has a disproportionate impact on your rights.

Your rights to access, rectify (correct), or erase (remove) your personal information may be limited because we need to handle your data in specific ways to ensure our research remains reliable and accurate. Meaning, if you change your mind about taking part, **we may not always be able to remove the information that we have already collected** (for example, if the information is anonymised and summarised and thus no longer traceable as 'your' information). The Participant Information Sheet will explain up to what point you can withdraw your data before it is anonymised and can no longer be linked to you.

We must carry out a request to erase personal data or to rectify personal data that is inaccurate, unless there are legal reasons under the UK GDPR that mean we can refuse.

If you want to exercise any of these rights or raise a complaint about how your personal data is handled, you can contact Michelle Evans at:

- michelle@giffnocksoccercentre.com

If you are unhappy with our response or think we are not handling your data properly, you can complain to the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) at <https://ico.org.uk/>

6.4. Appendix D – Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

Terms for taking part in the discussion:

I confirm that I have fully read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
I understand that my taking part is for research only, and not about judging me as a person.
I understand that taking part is my choice, and I can stop at any time during or after the discussion without giving a specific reason. This will not affect my legal rights. During the discussion, I can just tell the researcher(s) I want to leave and then leave. After the discussion, I have up to seven full days from when my discussion ends to ask for my data to be removed by emailing the researcher(s).
I understand that the discussion will be recorded (audio only) so that it can be typed up later (transcribed). The audio recordings will be uploaded from the voice recorders to OneDrive, where they will be stored safely until they are transcribed, whereupon they will be permanently deleted seven full days after the discussion ends.
I understand that when the discussion is transcribed, any information that could identify me or others (like names or places) will be made less specific to protect our privacy. Any quotes shared in the final report or other materials will be fully anonymised. I am aware that the report will be shared publicly.
I understand that demographic data (personal information such as age) will be collected through hard copy forms which will be typed up (into Excel) seven full days after the discussion ends. The Excel file will be uploaded into OneDrive, where it will be stored safely and permanently deleted once summary statistics has been calculated.
I understand that any demographic data that could identify me or others (like age or gender identity) will be summarised into group statistics to avoid identification of individuals.
I understand that hard copies of my signed Consent Form will be destroyed after photocopying, which will start seven full days after the discussion ends.
If I want all my data to be permanently deleted, I will email the researcher(s). I understand that if I leave during the discussion but do not ask for my data to be removed, any information collected before I leave will still be kept and used for analysis and the writing of the report.
I confirm that I agree to the way my data will be collected and processed. I understand that the report (containing summarised and anonymised data) and photocopies of my signed Consent Form will be stored permanently in Michelle Evans' GSC Auldhouse Foundation OneDrive, following relevant Data Protection policies and regulations.
I agree to take part in the research.

Please confirm that you agree with the information given, and that you consent to the terms above. Check **ONE** box only (using ✓):

- Yes, I have read the Participant Information Sheet, Privacy Notice and Consent Form and AGREE to take part in this discussion.
- No, I do NOT CONSENT to take part. The consultation will finish here.

Declaration

I confirm that the information I have provided is accurate and complete to the best of my knowledge.

Your signature: _____
Print full name: _____
Date: _____

6.5. Appendix E – Demographics Form

DEMOGRAPHICS FORM

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

Please answer the following.

Your answers will help us to better understand who is taking part and will help us ensure we hear from a wide range of people.

Your name or personal details will not be shared in the report. The personal information you provide (like age group or how long you've lived in the area) will only be used to create summary statistics. For example:

- “52% of participants were female”
- “40% of participants have lived in Ward 2 for over 5 years”

This means your answers will be combined with others to give an overall picture of our participants, not to identify individuals.

If we include quotes in the report, we will:

- Use a made-up name (pseudonym), such as “Participant A”
- Remove anything specific that could identify you

Example:

- **Participant A said:** “(My daughter) really likes Friday Night Football and has made lots of friends there. I work at (a local business), and Fridays are so busy, so it's nice that I can drop her off there for the evening.”

1. Which age group are you in?

Note that you must be 18 years old or over to take part in our discussion. Check

ONE box only (using ✓):

- Prefer not to say. The consultation will finish here.
- 17 years old or under. The consultation will finish here.
- 18 to 24 years old
- 25 to 34 years old
- 35 to 44 years old
- 45 to 54 years old
- 55 to 64 years old
- 65 to 74 years old
- 75 to 84 years old
- 85 years old or more

2. What is your connection to the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area?

Note only those who currently live in the area or have a strong connection to the community can take part. The Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area includes Arden, Kennishead, Carnwadric, Mansewood, Hillpark, Newlands, Muirend, Pollokshaws, and Eastwood. Below is a map of the area:

You can check **MORE THAN ONE** box (using ✓):

- Prefer not to say. The consultation will finish here.
 - I do NOT currently live in this area
 - I currently live here
 - I work, study or volunteer here
 - I run a business or organisation here
 - I use local services or facilities (e.g. shops, GP, library)
 - I have family or close friends who live here
 - I regularly visit for social or leisure reasons
 - Other – please say:
-

3. If you currently live in the Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area, how long have you lived here?

Check **ONE** box only (using ✓):

- Prefer not to say
- I do NOT currently live in this area.
- Less than 6 months
- 6 months to 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 10 years
- 10 years or more

4. What is your gender identity?

Check **ONE** box only (using ✓):

- Prefer not to say
- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other

5. What is your ethnic background?

Check **ONE** box only (using ✓):

- Prefer not to say
- Asian or Asian British
- Black, Black British, Caribbean or African
- White or European
- Indigenous Peoples
- Mixed or Multiple Ethnic Groups
- Other Ethnic Group

Declaration

I confirm that the information I have provided is accurate and complete to the best of my knowledge.

Your signature: _____

Print full name: _____

Date: _____

6.6. Appendix F – Discussion Questions

DISCUSSION QUESTIONS

Your Voice, Your Place: Shaping the New GSC Community Hub

Our team:

Sara Eftekhari, Liz Millard, and Michelle Evans

Prior to discussion:

- Check participants have read Participant Information Sheet & Privacy Notice and filled in the Consent & Demographics forms
- Business card - give one to each participant so they can contact us regarding rights, comments or queries
- MP3 recorders - check they work, then distribute so each participant has one near them
- Remind participants the community hub is about more than just football

Welcome & Introduction:

Hello! My name is Sara Eftekhari, and I will be the researcher leading the discussion today. Thank you for joining us!

Before we get started, a few housekeeping things:

- Does anyone have any questions or concerns about any of these forms or anything else about this discussion?
- For recording and transcription purposes just a reminder to try to speak clearly and not speak over each other
 - Raise your hand
- Please put away any devices or distractors (phones on silent)

General reminders:

- You do not have to answer any question you do not feel comfortable answering or do not want to answer
- This session will be audio recorded and auto-transcribed
- Anonymisation! Data protection!
- After this focus group is over, the recordings and data will be kept safe on OneDrive and the transcript anonymised then deleted after the report is written up. The consent & demographics forms will be digitised and the hard copies destroyed. The digitised versions will be used to create summary statistics and then permanently deleted after the report is written up.
- Remember that everyone here has a responsibility to maintain confidentiality of the topics discussed in the group and to please not share any private information shared today
- You are free to leave during the session and/or withdraw consent at any point
- If you wish to withdraw consent after this session please email me. You have seven full days from the time this discussion ends to change your mind.

Recap:

GSC Auldhouse Foundation is creating a new community hub for the people of Ward 2 (Newlands/Auldburn) area. We want this hub to reflect **your** voice: what would help the people you care for, and what would support you in caring for them, both personally and professionally.

So we are inviting you to share your thoughts and experiences about supporting the local community, and any suggestions you may have.

1. Life in the Community

- To start, introduce yourself and how you're connected to this area, and what it's like living/working here.

2. Challenges Faced

- What are some challenges you or others in the community face (that the hub could help with)?
- Are there any specific issues that affect particular groups differently (e.g. new arrivals, disabled people, single parents, etc.)?

3. Community Needs

- In your opinion, what does this community need the most right now that the hub can provide?
- Are there services or support that you feel are missing (that the hub can provide)?
 - ... that would make the biggest positive difference?

4. Ideas to Help the Community

- What ideas do you have for the hub that could help the community?
 - Why do you think these would be effective or important?
- Who do you think should be involved in making these ideas happen?
 - e.g. FUNDERS, food, youth clubs etc. skilled workers, volunteers, money, services, advice (housing/legal), etc.

5. Making the New Hub Useful and Welcoming

- What would help the new community hub feel welcoming, comfortable, and inclusive?
- How could the hub support people who might not normally engage with services?
 - What would help build **trust** and encourage people to come to the hub?

6. Suggestions for Activities, Spaces, or Support Services

- What kinds of activities or events would you like to see in the hub?
- What spaces do you think are important in the building or outdoors?
 - For example, third spaces, quiet areas, prayer rooms, breastfeeding spaces, etc.
- Are there specific support services that the hub could offer to help you or others?

7. Closing

- Anything I missed/not covered? Or anything else that you'd like to add?
- Does anyone have any final questions, comments, or concerns?
 - Feedback for us for how to run interviews better moving forward.

That concludes the session! Thank everyone for sharing.

6.7. Appendix G – R Code for Ward 2 Population Statistics

```
library(tidyverse)

## — Attaching core tidyverse packages ————— tidyverse
## 2.0.0 —
## ✓ dplyr      1.1.4      ✓ readr      2.1.5
## ✓ forcats   1.0.0      ✓ stringr    1.5.1
## ✓ ggplot2   3.5.2      ✓ tibble     3.3.0
## ✓ lubridate 1.9.4      ✓ tidyr      1.3.1
## ✓ purrr     1.1.0
## — Conflicts ————— tidyverse_conflicts() —
## ✗ dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## ✗ dplyr::lag()     masks stats::lag()
## ⓘ Use the conflicted package (<http://conflicted.r-lib.org/>) to force
## all conflicts to become errors

# Age Distribution with Gender Split
age_distribution <- tibble(
  age_group = c(
    "80+",
    "70-79",
    "60-69",
    "50-59",
    "40-49",
    "30-39",
    "20-29",
    "10-19",
    "0-9"
  ),
  female = c(577, 945, 1487, 1628, 1530, 1997, 1603, 1268, 1386),
  male   = c(365, 804, 1397, 1626, 1529, 1917, 1587, 1372, 1375)
) %>%
  mutate(population = female + male)

# Country of Birth
country_of_birth <- tibble(
  country = c(
    "Scotland",
    "UK (other)",
    "Europe",
    "Other country"
  ),
  population = c(
    18948, 1441, 1352, 2651
  )
)

# Ethnic Group
ethnic_group <- tibble(
  ethnicity = c(
    "White",
```

```

    "Asian",
    "African/Caribbean",
    "Mixed/multiple",
    "Other ethnic group"
  ),
  population = c(
    19208, 3390, 799, 499, 496
  )
)

# Religion
religion <- tibble(
  religion = c(
    "Church of Scotland",
    "Roman Catholics",
    "Other Christians",
    "Muslims",
    "Other religion",
    "No religion"
  ),
  population = c(
    3434, 4881, 1186, 2697, 722, 9641
  )
)

# Main Language (Aged 3+)
main_language <- tibble(
  language = c(
    "English",
    "Gaelic",
    "Scots",
    "British Sign Language",
    "Other language"
  ),
  population = c(
    21026, 6, 48, 27, 2418
  )
)

# Age Distribution: Population Pyramid
ggplot(age_distribution) +
  geom_col(aes(x = age_group, y = female, fill = "Female"), width = 0.8)
+
  geom_col(aes(x = age_group, y = -male, fill = "Male"), width = 0.8) +
  coord_flip() +
  scale_y_continuous(labels = abs) +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Gender") +
  labs(
    x = "Age Group (Years)",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw()

```

```

# Country of Birth: Bar Chart
ggplot(country_of_birth, aes(x = reorder(country, -population), y = population, fill = country)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Country") +
  labs(
    x = "Country of Birth",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

# Ethnic Group: Bar Chart
ggplot(ethnic_group, aes(x = reorder(ethnicity, -population), y = population, fill = ethnicity)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Ethnicity") +
  labs(
    x = "Ethnic Group",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

# Religion: Bar Chart
ggplot(religion, aes(x = reorder(religion, -population), y = population, fill = religion)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Religion") +
  labs(
    x = "Religion",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "none",
    axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 25, hjust = 1) # rotate labels
  )

# Main Language (Aged 3+): Bar Chart
ggplot(main_language, aes(x = reorder(language, -population), y = population, fill = language)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Language") +
  labs(
    x = "Language",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

```

6.8. Appendix H – R Code for Sample Statistics

```
library("tidyverse")
## — Attaching core tidyverse packages ————— tidyvers
e 2.0.0 —
## ✓ dplyr      1.1.4      ✓ readr      2.1.5
## ✓ forcats   1.0.0      ✓ stringr    1.5.1
## ✓ ggplot2   3.5.2      ✓ tibble     3.3.0
## ✓ lubridate 1.9.4      ✓ tidyr      1.3.1
## ✓ purrr     1.1.0
## — Conflicts ————— tidyverse_conf
licts() —
## ✗ dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## ✗ dplyr::lag()     masks stats::lag()
## i Use the conflicted package (<http://conflicted.r-lib.org/>) to force
  all conflicts to become errors

dat_demog <- read_csv("demographics_data.csv")

## Rows: 29 Columns: 8
## — Column specification —————
## Delimiter: ","
## chr (7): name, group, age, connection, duration, gender, ethnicity
## dbl (1): participant_ID
##
## i Use `spec()` to retrieve the full column specification for this dat
a.
## i Specify the column types or set `show_col_types = FALSE` to quiet th
is message.

dat <- "demographics_data.csv"

# STEP 1: Checks if a saved data file already exists
if (file.exists(dat)) {

# If the file exists, reads it into R so data can be entered into it
  dat_demog <- read_csv(dat, show_col_types = FALSE)

} else {

# If no file exists yet, creates a new empty tibble (table) with the foll
owing column names and types
  dat_demog <- tibble(
    participant_ID = integer(),      # participant ID as a whole number (e.
g., 1, 2, 3)
    name = character(),             # participant name as text
    group = character(),           # group is text (e.g., "P" for The Peo
ple, "PWLAP" for People Who Look After the People)
    age = character(),             # age group as a text (e.g., "18-24")
    connection = character(),      # connection to area and can store mul
tiple connections as comma-separated text (e.g., "I currently live here,
I work, study or volunteer here")
    duration = character(),        # duration of living in Ward 2 as text
```

```

(e.g., "3 to 5 years")
  gender = character(),           # gender is text (e.g., "Female", "Non
-binary")
  ethnicity = character()         # ethnicity is text (e.g., "Asian or A
sian British")
)
}

# STEP 2: Defines a function that can be used to add a new participant's
demographic data to the table
add_participant <- function(participant_ID, name, group, age, connection,
duration, gender, ethnicity) {

# Creates a new row in the table with the participant's typed-in demograp
hic data
new_entry <- tibble(
  participant_ID = participant_ID,
  name = name,
  group = group,
  age = age,
  connection = connection,
  duration = duration,
  gender = gender,
  ethnicity = ethnicity
)

# Adds the new row to the existing demographics table
# The <<- symbol updates the global variable (not just inside the functio
n)
dat_demog <<- bind_rows(dat_demog, new_entry)

# Saves the updated table back to the CSV file so changes are not lost
write_csv(dat_demog, dat)

# Prints a message and shows the current state of the table
message("Participant added. Current tibble:")
print(dat_demog)
}

# Enter a new row of participant demographics data into the table by runn
ing the following
#add_participant(
# participant_ID = ,
# name = "",
# group = "",
# age = "",
# connection = "",
# duration = "",
# gender = "",
# ethnicity = ""
#)

```

```

# Deletes the designated row number (e.g. -2 for row 2, -1 for row 1, et
c.)
#dat_demog <- dat_demog %>% slice(-)

#print(dat_demog)

# Edits a cell for a specific participant in a particular column
#dat_demog <- dat_demog %>%
# mutate(column = if_else(participant_ID == , "", column))

# Identify mismatches
mismatch_rows <- dat_demog %>%
# Remove extra spaces in connection just in case
  mutate(connection = str_trim(connection)) %>%
  filter(
# Either duration says "I do NOT currently live here" but connection does
  not contain it
    (duration == "I do NOT currently live here" & !str_detect(connection,
    "I do NOT currently live here")) |
# Or connection contains "I do NOT currently live here" but duration is n
ot equal to it
    (str_detect(connection, "I do NOT currently live here") & duration !=
    "I do NOT currently live here")
  )

mismatch_rows

# Correcting the mismatched rows
dat_demog <- dat_demog %>%
  mutate(
# Append "I do NOT currently live here" to connection if duration says it
  but connection does not
    connection = case_when(
      duration == "I do NOT currently live here" & !str_detect(connectio
n, "I do NOT currently live here") ~
      paste(connection, "I do NOT currently live here", sep = ","),
      TRUE ~ connection
    ),
# Set duration to "I do NOT currently live here" if connection contains i
t but duration does not
    duration = case_when(
      str_detect(connection, "I do NOT currently live here") & duration !
= "I do NOT currently live here" ~
      "I do NOT currently live here",
      TRUE ~ duration
    )
  )

# Age
age_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  count(age, name = "n") %>%
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>% # calculate percentage

```

```

  arrange(desc(n))
age_summary

## # A tibble: 8 × 3
##   age          n percent
##   <chr>      <int> <dbl>
## 1 35-44         12  41.4
## 2 25-34          4  13.8
## 3 18-24          3  10.3
## 4 55-64          3  10.3
## 5 65-74          3  10.3
## 6 45-54          2   6.90
## 7 75-84          1   3.45
## 8 85 or more     1   3.45

# Connection
connection_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  separate_rows(connection, sep = ",") %>%
  mutate(connection = str_trim(connection)) %>%
  count(connection, name = "n") %>%
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>%
  arrange(desc(n))
connection_summary

## # A tibble: 8 × 3
##   connection                                n per
cent
##   <chr>                                <int> <
dbl>
## 1 I currently live here                    19  2
5.7
## 2 I have family or close friends who live here  15  2
0.3
## 3 I work or study or volunteer here          15  2
0.3
## 4 I use local services or facilities         11  1
4.9
## 5 I do NOT currently live here              9   1
2.2
## 6 I regularly visit for social or leisure reasons  3
4.05
## 7 I regularly visit for social for social or leisure reasons  1
1.35
## 8 I run a business or organisation here       1
1.35

# Duration
duration_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  count(duration, name = "n") %>%
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>%
  arrange(desc(n))
duration_summary

## # A tibble: 8 × 3
##   duration                                n percent

```

```

##   <chr>                                <int>   <dbl>
## 1 I do NOT currently live here         9    31.0
## 2 10 or more                           7    24.1
## 3 5-10                                  5    17.2
## 4 1-3                                   3    10.3
## 5 Prefer not to say                    2     6.90
## 6 3-5                                   1     3.45
## 7 6 months to 1 year                   1     3.45
## 8 under 6 months                       1     3.45

# Create a separate variable for duration among current residents
duration_current <- dat_demog %>%
  filter(!duration %in% c("I do NOT currently live here", "Prefer not to
say")) %>%
  count(duration, name = "n") %>%           # count remaining durations
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>%   # recalc percent among remaini
ng
  arrange(desc(n))
duration_current

## # A tibble: 6 × 3
##   duration      n percent
##   <chr>        <int>   <dbl>
## 1 10 or more      7    38.9
## 2 5-10           5    27.8
## 3 1-3            3    16.7
## 4 3-5            1     5.56
## 5 6 months to 1 year 1     5.56
## 6 under 6 months  1     5.56

# Filter for participants whose duration says "I do NOT currently live he
re"
duration_not_live <- dat_demog %>%
  filter(duration == "I do NOT currently live here") %>%
  count(group, name = "n") %>%           # count by group
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100)     # calculate percentage within
this subset
duration_not_live

## # A tibble: 1 × 3
##   group      n percent
##   <chr> <int>   <dbl>
## 1 PWLAP     9    100

# Gender
gender_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  count(gender, name = "n") %>%
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>%
  arrange(desc(n))
gender_summary

## # A tibble: 3 × 3
##   gender      n percent
##   <chr>        <int>   <dbl>
## 1 Female      22    75.9

```

```

## 2 Male          5  17.2
## 3 Prefer not to say  2   6.90

# Ethnicity
ethnicity_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  count(ethnicity, name = "n") %>%
  mutate(percent = n / sum(n) * 100) %>%
  arrange(desc(n))
ethnicity_summary

## # A tibble: 3 × 3
##   ethnicity          n percent
##   <chr>          <int> <dbl>
## 1 White or European    20  69.0
## 2 Asian or Asian British    8  27.6
## 3 Mixed or Multiple Ethnic Groups    1   3.45

# Age (smallest to Largest)
age_levels <- c("18-24", "25-34", "35-44", "45-54", "55-64", "65-74", "75-84", "85 or more")
age_summary <- age_summary %>%
  mutate(age = factor(age, levels = age_levels))

ggplot(age_summary, aes(x = age, y = n, fill = age)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Age Group") +
  labs(
    x = "Age Group (Years)",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

# Connection
connection_summary <- dat_demog %>%
  separate_rows(connection, sep = ",") %>%
  mutate(connection = str_trim(connection)) %>%
  count(connection, name = "n") %>%
# Arrange descending by count, but keep "I do NOT currently live here" at
# the end
  arrange(desc(n)) %>%
  mutate(
    connection = factor(
      connection,
      levels = c(
        connection[connection != "I do NOT currently live here"], # all
except that one
        "I do NOT currently live here" # put
Last
      )
    )
  )

```

```

ggplot(connection_summary, aes(x = connection, y = n, fill = connection))
+
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Connection") +
  labs(
    x = "Connection to Area",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "none",
    axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1)
  )

# Duration (smallest to Largest)
duration_levels <- c("under 6 months", "6 months to 1 year", "1-3", "3-5",
  "5-10", "10 or more", "Prefer not to say", "I do NOT currently live here")
duration_summary <- duration_summary %>%
  mutate(duration = factor(duration, levels = duration_levels))

ggplot(duration_summary, aes(x = duration, y = n, fill = duration)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Duration") +
  labs(
    x = "Duration of Living in Ward 2 (Years, unless otherwise specified)",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none", axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 25,
hjust = 1))

# Gender
ggplot(gender_summary, aes(x = reorder(gender, -n), y = n, fill = gender)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Gender") +
  labs(
    x = "Gender",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

# Ethnicity
ggplot(ethnicity_summary, aes(x = reorder(ethnicity, -n), y = n, fill = ethnicity)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Ethnicity") +
  labs(
    x = "Ethnic Group",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +

```

```

theme_bw() +
theme(legend.position = "none")

# Define original order
duration_levels <- c(
  "under 6 months",
  "6 months to 1 year",
  "1-3",
  "3-5",
  "5-10",
  "10 or more",
  "Prefer not to say",
  "I do NOT currently live here"
)

# Recode Labels but keep order
duration_summary <- duration_summary %>%
  mutate(duration = factor(duration, levels = duration_levels),
         duration_label = factor(
           case_when(
             duration == "1-3" ~ "1-3 years",
             duration == "3-5" ~ "3-5 years",
             duration == "5-10" ~ "5-10 years",
             duration == "10 or more" ~ "10 years or more",
             TRUE ~ as.character(duration)
           ),
         levels = c(
           "under 6 months",
           "6 months to 1 year",
           "1-3 years",
           "3-5 years",
           "5-10 years",
           "10 years or more",
           "Prefer not to say",
           "I do NOT currently live here"
         )
  )
))

# Plot
ggplot(duration_summary, aes(x = duration_label, y = n, fill = duration_label)) +
  geom_col() +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(option = "E", name = "Duration") +
  labs(
    x = "Duration of Living in Ward 2",
    y = "Population Count"
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "none",
    axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 25, hjust = 1)
  )
)

```